

D 1.2

State-of-the-art analysis of public perceptions and reactions to hydrogen and fuel cell technologies

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Partners short names

APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
BH2C	Balkanski Vodoroden Klaster
CLUSTER TWEED	Cluster Tweed
CNH2	Centro Nacional Del Hidrogeno
ENVI	Parco Scientifico Tecnologico Per L'ambiente Environment Park Torino Spa
IME	Fundacion IMDEA Energia
IMI	Institute for Methods Innovation
RIGP	Regionalna Izba Gospodarcza Pomorza

Abbreviations

HFCT	Hydrogen fuel cell technologies
NIMBY	Not in my backyard
FCEV	Hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicle
FCH	Hydrogen fuel cell

Executive summary

Scope

The deliverable is divided into two main parts. The first section identifies and synthesises the existing research literature on public perceptions of hydrogen energy. The second section presents results from a secondary analysis of public opinion data about hydrogen energy in Europe.

This deliverable presents an original analysis of data collected for the Public Opinion Survey on hydrogen technology (Gallup International, 2023). By analysing existing survey data, we developed a baseline understanding of the public opinion regarding H2 implementation in EU countries regarding technology understanding and acceptance. Other reliable sources of survey data with analytical relevance to public understanding and acceptance of hydrogen technology in EU27 countries were explored and included in the literature review section of the deliverable.

Results

Literature review

In the context of decarbonising energy supply, the European public's perception of hydrogen technology is characterised by knowledge, cultural predispositions, and varying degrees of societal acceptance, influenced by regional specifics and overarching trends. Support for hydrogen technology often does not correlate with a comprehensive understanding of its mechanisms or implications. Instead, environmental concern and trust in scientific advancements significantly shape attitudes. This trend highlights the critical role of cultural predispositions, which strengthen with increased knowledge and influence acceptance as understanding grows.

While there is general positivity towards hydrogen technology across Europe, this support often encounters hurdles when implementing related infrastructure, particularly in residential areas. This is most evident in Germany, where public approval for hydrogen is high, yet local projects like hydrogen pipelines face resistance due to the 'Not in my backyard' (NIMBY) phenomenon. Similar challenges are seen in Denmark and Poland, where enthusiasm for hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEVs) and other applications is tempered by cost, infrastructure, and safety concerns. These insights suggest that while the foundational support exists largely due to perceived environmental benefits, it is conditional, requiring targeted communication strategies to address safety concerns and infrastructural hesitations.

Secondary analysis of public opinion data

The original analysis of public opinion survey data across the EU27 conducted for this deliverable reveals a broad awareness but limited in-depth understanding of hydrogen technology. Over 80% of respondents are aware of hydrogen energy at some level. However, there is a notable gender disparity in familiarity, with men claiming greater knowledge. This may link to a broader need to expand inclusion of women in STEM within the EU.

Ultimately EU13 countries evinced a broad range of views about hydrogen technology, sometimes more supportive than the EU27 and sometimes less. In EU13 nations such as Bulgaria and Malta, there is a strong belief in hydrogen's environmental benefits. At the same time, scepticism about its safety persists in some EU13 countries such as Czechia, Slovakia, and Bulgaria due to variable trust in new technologies and regulatory frameworks.

Implications for public engagement

Enhancing public acceptance and support for hydrogen technology in Europe necessitates a multifaceted approach that integrates continuous, effective information dissemination with robust, trust-building communication strategies. This approach should clarify the benefits and safety of hydrogen technology and tackle the infrastructural and economic concerns that inhibit broader acceptance. Emphasising the environmental advantages while transparently addressing practical and safety issues could foster a more informed and supportive public, pivotal for advancing hydrogen technology as a key part of Europe's green energy transition and decarbonisation efforts. This public engagement strategy aligns with findings from across the EU27, where the path to acceptance is paved with informed public engagement and policy-driven support.

1 Introduction

This report is a deliverable for the HYPOP project with the goal of understanding public opinion on hydrogen technology, focusing on understanding and acceptance. It contains a literature review of relevant data sources and a secondary analysis of data from a previously conducted Public Opinion Survey on hydrogen technology in EU27 countries (Gallup International, 2023). This deliverable, led by The Institute for Methods Innovation (IMI), provides a baseline and enhances the robustness of the original research, informing the development of public engagement workshops planned for WP3.

2 Literature review on public perceptions and reactions to hydrogen

This literature review sets out the state of the art for existing published research on public perceptions and reactions to hydrogen energy. Its purpose is to present key findings from reliable sources of survey data with analytical relevance to public understanding and acceptance of hydrogen technology in the European Union's 27 member states (EU27).

2.1 Literature review methodology

We conducted a rapid evidence assessment of the literature, broadly following the well-established PRISMA process (Page, et al, 2020), which provides guidelines to help systematic reviewers clearly explain why the review was conducted, detail the methods used, and summarize the findings.

A literature search was performed using Google Scholar using the search terms: '((COUNTRY) AND Hydrogen AND (public opinion OR public perception) AND survey)'. The search was repeatedly run, replacing the term 'COUNTRY' with each of the EU27 countries and 'Europe'. Following the flow diagram structure (Figure 1), the ten most relevant (as assigned by Google Scholar) hits were selected for each search. This produced 280 (EU27 countries +10 for "Europe") initial hits. After deduplication, the number of records was reduced to 153 unique entries. These were then screened by 'Title' and 'Abstract', and if they contained the words 'Hydrogen,' they were included in the next screening stage; otherwise, they were excluded. The 58 texts taken to full-text screening were then examined in more detail to establish whether they met core inclusion criteria (they referred to public perceptions, were EU-focused, and contained some form of survey data collection). Texts where there was uncertainty as to whether to include were discussed and a decision was collectively made (n=6). A total of 28 were selected in full text. ChatGPT was used in combination with author screening to summarise literature content.

In addition to systematic searches, hand searches were conducted. This involved opportunistic web searches using the terms 'hydrogen' and iterations of the terms 'acceptance', 'opinion', 'interest', 'attitudes', 'support', and 'knowledge'. This identified two additional unique sources relevant to the review. All searches were conducted in English, aligning with the EU's primary language for policy documents, ensuring a coherent contextual understanding. Despite the existence of surveys in other languages, focusing on English texts provided diverse examples from across the EU27 without compromising the search's robustness, demonstrating the effectiveness of using a widely understood language.

Figure 1. Flow chart detailing text selection following PRISMA guidelines

Here is an overview of relevant sources identified by this review of survey data with analytical relevance to public understanding and acceptance of hydrogen technology in the EU27 (Table 1). Each identified relevant source is summarised in Section 2, followed by a discussion of the substantive findings gleaned from these sources.

Table 1. Relevant sources of survey data with analytical relevance

#	Source type	Title	Link
1	Journal article	Unknowing but supportive? Predispositions, knowledge, and support for hydrogen technology in the Netherlands	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2010.03.091
2	Journal article	The role of attitudes in technology acceptance management: Reflections on the case of hydrogen fuel cells in Europe	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.03.266
3	Journal article	Dynamic effects on the acceptance of hydrogen technologies—an international comparison	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2008.02.068
4	Journal article	Are French people ready to accept hydrogen underground storage? An answer through the distance from object model	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.02.077
5	Journal article	Hydrogen in future energy systems: Social acceptance of the technology and its large-scale infrastructure	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.05.160
6	Journal article	Let's go green with hydrogen! The general public's perspective	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2012.02.126
7	Journal article	Knowing hydrogen and loving it too? Information provision, cultural predispositions, and support for hydrogen technology among the Dutch.	https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662512453117
8	Journal article	Public acceptance of hydrogen in the Netherlands: Two surveys that demystify public views on a hydrogen economy	https://doi.org/10.1177/0270467606290308
9	Journal article	A survey of Finnish energy engineering students' knowledge and perception of hydrogen technology	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2018.04.098
10	Journal article	Assessing the social acceptance of hydrogen for transportation in Spain: An unintentional focus on target population for a potential hydrogen economy	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2016.01.139

11	Conference paper	Forecasting the passenger car demand split from public perceptions of electric, hybrid, and hydrogen-fuelled cars in Greece	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-23721-8_6
12	Journal article	Is the public willing to pay for hydrogen buses? A comparative study of preferences in four cities	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2006.12.031

13	Journal article	Social acceptance of green hydrogen in Germany: building trust through responsible innovation	https://doi.org/10.1186/s13705-023-00394-4
14	Journal article	The changing face of public support for hydrogen technology explaining declining support among the Dutch (2008–2013)	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2014.08.053
15	Journal article	Willingness to pay and public acceptance for hydrogen buses: A case study of Perugia	https://doi.org/10.3390/su71013270
16	Journal article	A positive shift in the public acceptability of a low-carbon energy project after implementation: The case of a hydrogen fuel station	https://doi.org/10.3390/su11082220
17	Journal article	Hydrogen as Energy Source – Challenges for Regions in Latvia (Results of Public Opinion Survey)	10.15544/mts.2014.014
18	Journal article	Hydrogen energy as a catalyst for sustainable development: A comparative analysis of policies, strategies, and implementation in Poland and Germany	http://dx.doi.org/10.29119/1641-3466.2023.179.37
19	Conference proceedings	Opportunities for hydrogen marketing - Public opinion analysis (New challenges of economic and business development – 2012, Latvia)	ISBN 978-9984-45-519-78
20	Journal article	People's attitude to energy from hydrogen—from the point of view of modern energy technologies and social responsibility	https://doi.org/10.3390/en13246495

21	Journal article	Prospects of the hydrogen-based mobility in the private vehicle market. A social perspective in Denmark	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.11.167
22	Master's degree dissertation	Public perceptions of hydrogen as an energy vector and aid to decarbonisation in the Republic of Ireland	https://sword.cit.ie/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1009&context=buses
23	Journal article	Risk assessment for hydrogen fuelling stations: Public perception versus reality	https://doi.org/10.3303/CET23105024
24	Journal article	Stakeholders' perceptions of hydrogen and reflections on energy transition governance	https://doi.org/10.1186/s13705-023-00429-w
25	Journal article	Assessing the social acceptance of key technologies for the German energy transition	https://doi.org/10.1186/s13705-021-00329-x
26	Journal article	Toward low-carbon European Union society: Young Poles' perception of climate neutrality	https://doi.org/10.3390/en14165107
27	Journal article	Public acceptance of biofuels in the transport sector in Finland	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijisbe.2017.07.008

28	Journal article	Public acceptance of emerging energy technologies in context of the German energy transition	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111516
29	Project report	Accept H2: public perception of hydrogen buses in five countries	https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=c5b4e2e26f96e8d5a6ca3be46f39087fff0ebb4a
30	European Commission project deliverable	Hydrogen acceptance in the transition phase (HYACINTH) D5.2: General findings on public acceptance	https://hyacinthproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/HYACINTH-D5_2-General-findings-on-public-acceptance_DEF.pdf

Countries represented by articles included in the review

The review covered the representation of EU countries in studies on public perceptions of hydrogen technologies (Table 2). Of the EU27 countries, 24 were represented, with Malta, Cyprus, and Sweden absent due to not meeting the inclusion criteria (i.e., written in English, survey data, EU-based, and focused on public perceptions of hydrogen). Germany contributed to the most studies (n=12), followed by the Netherlands and Spain. Most countries were represented in one or two studies, with some studies including opinions from multiple countries, indicating broad yet uneven coverage.

Data spanned from 2005 to 2024, showing an increase in studies post-2015. The earliest studies (2005-2010) focused predominantly on Germany, the Netherlands, Luxembourg, and Spain. While many studies had large sample sizes (1,000 or more respondents per country), some featured smaller samples, raising concerns about representativeness. Notably, the most recent study, with relatively low respondent numbers, served as the sole source for viewpoints from eight countries, including six from the EU13, highlighting the need for more comprehensive data from these nations.

Table 2. Countries represented by the relevant articles/reports identified by the literature review

Country	No. of studies	Reference
EU27 general	1	19
Germany	12	2, 3, 5, 6, 11, 13, 18, 24, 25, 28, 29, 30
Netherlands	6	1, 3, 7, 8, 14, 16
Spain	6	2, 3, 10, 23, 24, 30
Poland	4	18, 20, 24, 26
Luxembourg	3	3, 11, 29
France	3	2, 4, 30
Belgium	2	2, 30
Czechia	2	20, 24
Finland	2	9, 27
Greece	2	11, 24
Slovakia	2	20, 24
Slovenia	2	2, 24, 30
Austria	1	24
Bulgaria	1	24
Croatia	1	24
Denmark	1	21
Estonia	1	24
Hungary	1	24
Ireland	1	22
Italy	1	15
Latvia	1	17
Lithuania	1	24
Portugal	1	24
Romania	1	24
Cyprus	0	0
Malta	0	0
Sweden	0	0

2.2 Literature review results: Summaries of relevant research studies

Source 1. **Unknowing but supportive? Predispositions, knowledge, and support for hydrogen technology in the Netherlands (2010)**

The study investigates the Dutch public's knowledge of and support for hydrogen technology, revealing a generally low level of hydrogen knowledge yet high support for its implementation. This paradox prompts exploration into the role of cultural predispositions—such as environmental concern and trust in technology—in shaping public opinion towards hydrogen technology. Drawing on a representative survey conducted in 2008 (N = 2121), the research uncovers that while factual knowledge about hydrogen positively influences support, cultural predispositions hold more sway in determining public acceptance. Specifically, individuals with high trust in technology and environmental concerns exhibit stronger support for hydrogen technology. Furthermore, the study finds that the impact of cultural predispositions on hydrogen technology support intensifies with an increase in relevant knowledge, highlighting the nuanced interplay between information, predispositions, and public support.

“

For those culturally predisposed to favour hydrogen technology the addition of adequate knowledge leads to more favourable judgments of hydrogen technology.

”

Source 2. **The role of attitudes in technology acceptance management: reflections on the case of hydrogen fuel cells in Europe (2018)**

The study explores the impact of public attitudes on the acceptance of hydrogen fuel cell technologies across seven European countries (Belgium, France, Germany, Norway, Slovenia, Spain and the United Kingdom). The survey results (N = +/- 1000 per country) highlight a general positivity towards hydrogen technologies but underline the low strength and stability of these attitudes due to limited public knowledge and awareness. The research suggests that at the early stages of technology diffusion, public attitudes are not yet strong enough to significantly influence reactions to communication campaigns to increase social acceptance or merely inform the public about hydrogen fuel cells.

“

For communication strategies aiming at technology diffusion, this implies that information campaigns are valuable at an early stage of hydrogen technology diffusion. Such campaigns will likely increase awareness for those without knowledge and positively influence attitudes towards the technology.

”

Source 3. Dynamic effects on the acceptance of hydrogen technologies—an international comparison (2008)

The study, conducted across eight cities (Amsterdam, Barcelona, Berlin, Hamburg, London, Luxembourg, Madrid and Reykjavik) with 3352 respondents, explores public acceptance of hydrogen technologies. It reveals 68% of respondents are supportive, while 31% show volatile attitudes. Interestingly, 77% preferred hydrogen buses over conventional ones under identical conditions, yet 21% remained indifferent. This discrepancy highlights that acceptance can shift based on new information or incidents. The research suggests that significant events could either boost support to 97% or increase opposition to 32%, emphasising the need for ongoing public engagement to stabilise and enhance acceptance of hydrogen technologies. Overall, the research shows that people who are neutral about hydrogen technologies and seek more information are easier to educate and persuade than those who are already opposed. Indifference and a desire for more knowledge create an opportunity for effective communication, whereas opposition requires overcoming preconceived negative attitudes.

People can be informed about and convinced of hydrogen technologies easier as long as they are indifferent and pronounce a need of more information than if they already form part of the opposition.

Source 4. Are French people ready to accept hydrogen underground storage? An answer through the distance from object model (2023)

The article explores the social acceptability of underground hydrogen storage in France. It focuses on how public perceptions are influenced by knowledge, experience, and personal involvement. A survey of 157 French respondents highlights generally positive attitudes toward hydrogen storage and believes it could protect the environment, considering environmental and fossil fuel issues important. Those with higher knowledge of hydrogen saw it as more beneficial for the environment, while those with lower knowledge perceived greater problems with fossil fuels. Key findings suggest that increasing knowledge about hydrogen's environmental impact and emphasising the importance of environmental issues can enhance public acceptance of hydrogen storage.

... results support the hypothesis that knowledge and socio-demographic variables impact perceptions of a project and show that analyses of French people's readiness to embrace hydrogen as a source of energy must also consider experience and involvement.

Source 5. Hydrogen in future energy systems: Social acceptance of the technology and its large-scale infrastructure (2021)

This study, part of the ELEGANCY project (SINTEF Energy Research, 2017), examines the social acceptance of hydrogen technology and its infrastructure in Germany. Survey data from 1,438 Germans reveal a generally positive view of hydrogen (65%), but acceptance drops when infrastructure, such as pipelines, is proposed locally. Younger respondents show more tendencies for Not-In-My-Back-Yard (NIMBY) than older respondents. Trust in stakeholders, particularly political and scientific entities, boosts acceptance levels, while low trust, especially in environmental NGOs, correlates with NIMBY attitudes.

The findings give new insights into the social potential of hydrogen as a central technology in the context of the energy transition. As already known from previous studies, hydrogen technology enjoys a rather positive perception in the population. However, the present results show a clear decreasing of acceptance when it comes to large-scale infrastructure in the neighbourhood.

Source 6. Let's go green with hydrogen! The general public's perspective (2012)

This study examines German public acceptance of hydrogen technology in the mobility sector, revealing that nearly 80% of Germans support the introduction of hydrogen vehicles. This positive outlook is contingent on hydrogen being produced in an environmentally friendly manner. The study, part of the HyTrust project (NOW GmbH, n.d.) and funded by the German Federal Ministry of Transport, employed interviews (N = 30), focus groups (N = 3), and a representative survey (N = 1011) to gauge public opinion. Despite high awareness and favourable attitudes towards hydrogen-powered cars, the public lacks detailed knowledge about hydrogen and fuel cell technology. The study indicates safety concerns are minimal, emphasizing the importance of renewable energy in hydrogen production for public support.

Regarding the general public's acceptance of hydrogen technology, political and business decision-makers should worry less about whether people will consider the technology unsafe and instead focus more on the issue that people expect the hydrogen on the market to actually have been produced with renewable energy.

Source 7. Knowing hydrogen and loving it too? Information provision, cultural predispositions, and support for hydrogen technology among the Dutch (2012)

The study investigates how information and cultural predispositions in the Netherlands shape public perceptions of hydrogen technology. The study explores the framing effects on public support by using 1,012 respondents provided with varying information about hydrogen technology. Findings suggest that for individuals with high trust in science and technology, positive information enhances support for hydrogen technology, whereas negative information diminishes it. Conversely, for those with low trust in science and technology, providing positive or negative information does not significantly influence their evaluation of hydrogen technology. This reveals a nuanced interaction between information provision and pre-existing cultural predispositions towards science and technology. This suggests that "providing positive information fails to evoke a more favourable evaluation" among those inherently sceptical of science and technology.

“

For those with high trust in science and technology, positive information increases support, while negative information detracts from it. For those with low trust in science and technology, however, information provision has no effect on evaluating hydrogen technology.

”

Source 8. Public acceptance of Hydrogen in the Netherlands: Two surveys that demystify public views on a hydrogen economy (2006)

The journal article examines the Dutch public's (n=612) acceptance of hydrogen technology through two surveys. The findings indicate a generally positive attitude towards hydrogen, albeit with significant variability based on the type of information presented to participants. Specifically, the study finds that 87% of respondents showed a favourable attitude towards using hydrogen combined with natural gas for home heating when exposed to positively skewed information about hydrogen. However, acceptance rates differed when participants were provided with negative or neutral information, demonstrating the impact of media framing on public perception. The surveys also addressed the public's willingness to accept trade-offs while transitioning to a hydrogen economy. For example, while a significant majority (87%) would support the use of hydrogen if it produced 10% less carbon dioxide than natural gas and maintained the same level of service, this support dropped to 67% if a 100-euro switch cost was involved, and to less than a third if safety was perceived to be slightly compromised.

“

...the research has shown that public acceptance of hydrogen is very vulnerable to perceptions of decreased safety and thus can be easily swayed by any negatively coloured information presented by the media.

”

Source 9. A survey of Finnish energy engineering students' knowledge and perception of hydrogen technology (2018)

The study, involving 93 students from Aalto University, assessed changes in their understanding and attitudes before and after a specific learning assignment focused on hydrogen technology. Key findings include significant improvements in students' knowledge, particularly regarding hydrogen safety, with an average increase of 1.74 points on a 6-point scale post-assignment. Additionally, students' willingness to adopt home hydrogen systems showed notable growth, highlighted by an increase from 2.78 to 4.06 on the same scale. This shift suggests a robust positive response to the educational content provided.

“

Topics related to hydrogen should be treated as a part of a larger system rather than as chemical reactions or single components. The development of teaching methods calls for the implementation of both radical and conventional problem settings that challenge the students to think in both a creative and realistic manner.

”

Source 10. Assessing the social acceptance of hydrogen for transportation in Spain (2016)

The study surveyed 1005 Spanish residents to evaluate public perception and acceptance of hydrogen as a potential energy carrier in the transportation sector. The respondents demonstrated a high level of awareness (>70%) about hydrogen and a favourable opinion on its implementation, with nearly 80% supporting hydrogen technologies in public transport and 75% endorsing its environmental benefits. The survey revealed strong public backing for establishing local hydrogen refuelling stations, although there was a preference for these to be located away from residential areas. The findings suggest that, while there is substantial support for hydrogen technologies, considerable work remains to address economic and infrastructural challenges to facilitate broader adoption.

“

Because the results of the survey are unintentionally associated with young population (18-35 years old) with university education level, the findings in terms of high social awareness, perception and support can be considered a promising forecast of the role of hydrogen in the mid- and long-term in Spain.

”

Source 11. Forecasting the passenger car demand split from public perceptions of electric, hybrid, and hydrogen-fuelled cars in Greece (2022)

The study aims to explore the feasibility of machine learning techniques to forecast the demand for passenger cars with motor units other than internal combustion engines (ICE). The authors used a multilayer perceptron and an adaptive neural fuzzy inference system (machine learning techniques) to forecast the demand split from public perceptions, captured through an online survey. The survey data was collected in March 2022 (n=453) to measure respondents' intent to buy a passenger car, including hydrogen electric vehicles. Researchers found less than 5% of respondents intended to buy a new or used hydrogen electric vehicle.

“

...if the government wishes to promote the adoption of alternative motor unit passenger cars over ICE ones, then it will need to alleviate the perception of high purchase cost, promote the perception of technological maturity, and advance higher paid stable occupation, as this greatly affects the choice for a new car...

”

Source 12. Is the public willing to pay for hydrogen buses? A comparative study of preferences in four cities (2007)

Using the contingent valuation method, the study evaluates the public's willingness to pay for hydrogen fuel cell buses across Berlin, London, Luxembourg, and Perth. This survey research took place between July 2003 and February 2004 and forms part of the AcceptH2 project and investigates public acceptance and preferences for this environmentally friendly transportation technology (n=1358 total; n=344 in Berlin; n=300 in Luxembourg). Findings show that the public in all surveyed cities is positively willing to pay for the air pollution reductions associated with hydrogen buses, with an adjusted willingness to pay extra, ranging from €0.29 to €0.35 per single bus fare. The study reveals that this willingness spans different geographic locations, indicating a generally positive reception towards hydrogen buses, irrespective of the specific urban context.

“

These results tentatively support, and add to, findings in the literature that the public is, overall, supportive of H2-transport technologies.

”

Source 13. Social acceptance of green hydrogen in Germany: Building trust through responsible innovation (2023)

The study delves into the public's perception and acceptance of green hydrogen technology in Germany. The research used a comprehensive mixed-method approach comprising semi-structured interviews (n=24), participatory workshops (n=51), and a representative survey (n=2054) to gauge social attitudes and derive generalisable conclusions about green hydrogen. The study unearthed a critical mix of limited knowledge yet considerable openness towards green hydrogen within the general population. It shows that acceptance hinges significantly on trust in scientific, governmental, and media institutions, which are key in upholding distributive justice. Additionally, the research identified methodologically sound participatory processes as catalysts for enhancing trust and acceptance, suggesting that positive experiences within these engagements are crucial for fostering social trust.

“

Our findings show participation to be an effective instrument for promoting acceptance in general and active support in particular, and that positive, participatory experiences can play an important role in fostering trust.

”

Source 14. The changing face of public support for hydrogen technology: Explaining declining support among the Dutch (2008-2013) (2014)

Using data from two surveys conducted in 2008 (n=2121) and 2013 (n=1982), the study found that while initially high, public support for hydrogen technology significantly declined by 2013. The decline in support was quantified through a series of F-tests revealing decreases in agreement with several statements about hydrogen technology: support for investment dropped from 84.8% to 79.2%, belief in its application in public transportation fell from 86.4% to 77.1%, agreement that it is good for the environment declined from 78.9% to 73.4%, and urgency for its adoption decreased from 45.7% to 35.6%. The research attributes this decline primarily to a corresponding drop in trust in science and technology over the same period. This shift is viewed through the lens of modern societal trends, suggesting that increased awareness of the risks associated with science and technology among the educated may undermine support for technological advancements such as hydrogen technology.

“

It is because public trust in science has declined that the public also decreasingly favours hydrogen technology. It needs to be noted, though, that even though we have witnessed a decline, there still is a majority of people who support hydrogen technology.

”

Source 15. Willingness to pay and public acceptance for hydrogen buses: A case study of Perugia (2015)

The study assessed public perception among local public transport users in Perugia, Italy, concerning air pollution reduction through hydrogen buses from the end of January to March 2013 (n=587). A significant portion of the survey sample expressed a willingness to pay a premium for hydrogen buses, highlighting the public's recognition of the environmental benefits these buses could offer. The findings indicate that 81% of respondents supported the trial of hydrogen buses, and 88% were willing to pay more for public transportation if it involved hydrogen technology. This reflects a public acceptance of hydrogen buses, predicated on the potential environmental benefits.

“

...citizens in Perugia have already reached a consensus with regard to H2B introduction and paying extra for related environmental improvements: 81% of the respondents agreed with the H2B trial in Perugia, and 88% stated their WTP for the introduction of H2B on a large-scale through an increase in bus fare.

”

Source 16. A positive shift in the public acceptability of a low-carbon energy project after implementation: The case of a hydrogen fuel station (2019)

The article investigates the changes in public acceptance of a hydrogen fuel station in Arnhem, Netherlands, before and after its implementation. The data collection (n=280) took place around the official opening of the hydrogen fuel station on December 3, 2010. The study reveals that residents living near the station showed a significant increase in acceptability post-implementation, contrary to those living farther away, who showed no significant change. This phenomenon is attributed to psychological mechanisms such as loss aversion and cognitive dissonance reduction.

“

...policy makers, project developers, and citizens should be aware that public acceptability can change after implementation among citizens who live in proximity to the technology.

”

Source 17. Hydrogen as Energy Source – Challenges for Regions in Latvia (Results of Public Opinion Survey) (2014)

The research explores the public's perception and acceptance of hydrogen energy across different regions of Latvia. Conducted in the first half of 2013, the study involved a comprehensive survey targeting various demographic groups, with a total of 1299 respondents, comprising 51.7% females and 48.3% males. The findings indicate a significant lack of public awareness and information about hydrogen energy, with average ratings on various aspects of hydrogen technology knowledge and acceptance falling on the lower end of the scale. Key results reveal that while there is widespread support for hydrogen technology, with 70.1% of respondents showing favourability, the public's detailed understanding of hydrogen energy applications in the economy and transport sector is notably low.

“

Society in general supports the implementation of renewable energy technologies in Latvia and would be interested in receiving more information in the media about the experience of hydrogen use in other countries.

”

Source 18. Hydrogen energy as a catalyst for sustainable development: A comparative analysis of policies, strategies, and implementation in Poland and Germany (2023)

The study presents a comparative analysis by reviewing literature, policy frameworks, and stakeholder surveys, highlighting how hydrogen is integrated into Poland and Germany's energy strategy. The survey component of this research took place in 2021 and involved a sample size of 898 people from Poland and 924 from Germany. In Poland, the implementation of hydrogen technology is still evolving, with a strong emphasis on research and development aimed at integrating hydrogen with renewable energy sources. The Polish government's proactive stance includes ambitious goals to make Poland a leader in hydrogen energy in Europe by 2030. Conversely, Germany is already a global leader in hydrogen technology, backed by a well-established and comprehensive strategy promoting commercialising hydrogen technologies across various sectors. Despite these advancements, both countries face high production costs and infrastructural demands.

“ Respondents in both nations consider environmental friendliness and innovation as primary benefits of hydrogen energy. Hydrogen is recognized as a potential competitive energy source, although perceptions of reliability and cost-effectiveness vary between the two nations. ”

Source 19. Opportunities for hydrogen marketing – Public opinion analysis (2012)

The article explores public receptiveness to hydrogen energy, focusing on the European market. The study surveyed 1200 participants across various demographics. The key findings include that 62% of respondents know hydrogen as an energy source, yet only 28% can clearly articulate its potential uses or benefits. Public support for hydrogen energy is moderate, with 48% expressing tentative support contingent on further information about environmental impacts and safety. The study highlights a gap in effective communication, as demonstrated by the fact that 72% of respondents were uncertain about hydrogen's safety, pointing to a need for targeted educational campaigns.

“ ...many respondents are highly concerned about safety issues of the renewable energy technology. This means that safety education must be implemented and discussed more with society. ”

Source 20. People's attitude to energy from hydrogen—from the point of view of modern energy technologies and social responsibility (2020)

The journal article provides a comprehensive analysis of public opinion on hydrogen energy, particularly focusing on its safety and environmental impacts. The study involved surveying (n=749) individuals in countries where hydrogen technology is underdeveloped and infrastructure is sparse (Poland (n=247), Czech Republic (n=223), and Slovakia (n=199)). The data collection period spanned from October 2019 to February 2020. The survey results indicate a significant lack of knowledge and familiarity with hydrogen energy among the public. Notably, while there is a foundational understanding that hydrogen can be an eco-friendly energy source, 78% of respondents expressed concerns about its safety. This scepticism highlights a significant barrier to wider acceptance and adoption of hydrogen energy technologies.

“

Knowledge about hydrogen as an energy source, and its production safety and storage methods, is very low.

”

Source 21. Prospects of hydrogen-based mobility in the private vehicle market. A social perspective in Denmark (2021)

The article focuses on the social acceptance and market prospects of hydrogen-based mobility in Denmark. It reports a considerable awareness and interest in hydrogen vehicles, revealing that knowledge about hydrogen technology and environmental awareness significantly influence the public's willingness to adopt such vehicles. The survey (n=158) found that 20% of respondents are ready to consider hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEVs) as a viable alternative to conventional cars, given the proper infrastructure and cost considerations. A pivotal finding is the public's sensitivity to the high initial costs and the lack of refuelling infrastructure, which are major barriers to adoption.

“

...the main obstacle identified to hinder the development of the FCEV market in Denmark is, on one hand, the limited PEOU (Ease of Use) of this technology, the lack of media support and the low number of refuelling infrastructure.

”

Source 22. Public perceptions of hydrogen as an energy vector and aid to decarbonisation in the Republic of Ireland (2021)

This master's degree dissertation examines how the public perceives hydrogen as an energy vector in the Republic of Ireland, outlining potential obstacles to its acceptance. The sample size for the quantitative survey component of this research was 115 respondents. Semi-structured qualitative interviews with eight participants followed this to gather more detailed data and insights into

public perceptions. The survey found that public perceptions of hydrogen as an energy vector are not entirely hostile, with broad acceptance evident, although some opposition to a transition was observed. The two overarching themes of this study are safety and cost. Safety is viewed as a prerequisite to any transition, with the public trusting that hydrogen safety will be demonstrated before a transition and that a competent authority will act with safety in mind. The cost of transitioning to hydrogen as an energy vector is vital to its acceptance by the public. Increased costs to consumers can result in the widespread rejection of conversion as concerns regarding cost far outweigh the environmental benefits of hydrogen among the public.

“

Trust is vital to a transition to hydrogen as it is a critical aspect of two parts of a transition: safety and information.

”

Source 23. Risk assessment for hydrogen fuelling stations: Public perception versus reality (2023)

The article addresses the discrepancy between public perceptions and the empirical risks associated with Hydrogen Fuelling Stations (HFSs) in Japan (n=1000), Spain (n=1000), and Norway (n=500). The study was conducted in December 2022 and explored perceptions of risk regarding the operations of HFSs—namely hydrogen production, transportation, storage, and dispensing. The findings reveal a notable gap in public understanding: participants often overestimate the risks associated with transportation and underestimate those related to production and storage. The empirical data from event tree analysis highlighted that incidents like ruptures or leaks at HFSs are less frequent than the public perceives. Despite the lower empirical risk, the perception of danger is significantly higher, particularly for transportation processes.

“

As the process that the public is most frequently exposed to, transportation is a window that reflects the safety of hydrogen application, mainly shaping the image of HFSs in the public's perception. Improving transportation safety and promoting knowledge, such as incorporating safety technology promotions on the bodies of heavy-duty trucks, can be an effective measure to increase public acceptance of hydrogen energy.

”

Source 24. Stakeholders' perceptions of hydrogen and reflections on energy transition governance (2024)

The research on stakeholders' perceptions of hydrogen and reflections on energy transition

governance was conducted under the European Union-funded 112CO2 Project. It involved semi-structured interviews and a questionnaire survey (n=73) with stakeholders across various countries, largely within Europe (Germany, South Africa, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Croatia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, India, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Qatar, Romania, Serbia). The interviews were conducted from January to June 2022, while the questionnaire survey took place between July and December 2022. The findings reveal a strong preference for renewable hydrogen over non-renewable sources. Specifically, all respondent groups shared this preference, highlighting a consensus on the sustainability priorities within the hydrogen production debate. Key findings from the questionnaire indicate that 76.7% of stakeholders believe hydrogen must be produced from exclusively renewable sources, even if this results in higher costs. Conversely, nearly half of the participants are against hydrogen production from non-renewable sources, even if mixed with renewable sources to reduce costs.

“

The findings suggest a tendency to favour hydrogen produced from renewable sources and to reject hydrogen produced from non-renewable sources. All the examined groups conform to this pattern.

”

“

The participants identify hydrogen as a matter that remained unnoticed for over a decade, despite its prominent position in the policies and economic approaches of numerous countries.

”

Source 25. Assessing the social acceptance of key technologies for the German energy transition (2022)

The study evaluates public attitudes towards three energy technologies: stationary battery storage, biofuel production plants, and hydrogen refuelling stations (n=1247). Conducted as part of the German energy transition initiative, the survey reveals nuanced insights into general and local acceptance levels, trust in stakeholders, and financial support attitudes among the German public. General acceptance for hydrogen refuelling stations was comparatively high, reflecting broad support for this technology as part of Germany's energy transition. However, while still positive, local acceptance was slightly lower than general acceptance, demonstrating the common "general-local gap" where public support wanes when installation near residential areas is proposed.

“

With regard to hydrogen refuelling stations, explosion hazards (64%) and fire hazards (37%) were the most frequently mentioned concerns.

”

Source 26. Toward low-carbon European Union society: Young Poles' perception of climate neutrality (2021)

The journal article explores young Polish students' perspectives on energy and environmental awareness, specifically emphasising hydrogen as a renewable energy source. The survey was conducted (n=1106) from January to May 2021. The findings reveal a significant interest among the youth in embracing hydrogen technologies. Specifically, the study finds that hydrogen is regarded as a promising energy carrier due to its high energy content and versatility in applications ranging from power generation to transportation. The article suggests the critical role of hydrogen in achieving the European Union's climate neutrality goals, reflecting a strong alignment between technological potential and policy aspirations.

“

The limited scope of young Poles' understanding of energy changes and the European Union's strive for a low-carbon society create demand for structural educational changes in Poland.

”

Source 27. Public acceptance of biofuels in the transport sector in Finland (2017)

The research on public acceptance of biofuels in the transport sector in Finland was conducted in the capital region, specifically in Helsinki, Espoo, and Vantaa (n=90). Data collection took place from April to June 2016. It highlights that despite a significant governmental push towards biofuels, public knowledge and acceptance are crucial for broader adoption. The study's findings indicate that 63% of car owners prefer ideal future fuel to be non-biofuel based: 60% favour electricity, 20% hydrogen, and another 20% prefer hybrid solutions.

Source 28. Public acceptance of emerging energy technologies in context of the German energy transition (2020)

The study (n=1247) investigates public acceptance of hydrogen fuel stations, among other technologies. It leverages a socio-psychological factor model to explore how trust in industry and municipalities, perceived problems of the current energy system, and environmental self-identity impact acceptance generally and when these technologies are implemented locally. Specifically, hydrogen fuel stations (HFS) were one of the technologies studied for their potential to replace

fossil fuels. The findings indicate varying degrees of acceptance influenced by several factors, including trust and perceived risks and benefits. The study reveals that the general acceptance of hydrogen fuel stations hinges significantly on perceived environmental benefits and trust in the industrial stakeholders pushing their development, notably the automotive industry. Additionally, the presence of hydrogen fuel stations in local settings tends to be more acceptable when there is significant trust in local municipalities.

“

As the factors trust in industry and trust in municipalities explain both local and general acceptance for the different technologies, we recommend that industry and municipalities strengthen their relationships of trust with the public to increase local and general acceptance.

”

Source 29. Accept H2: public perception of hydrogen buses in five countries (2004)

The international study focuses on understanding public perception and acceptance of hydrogen buses within public transport. Conducted across London (UK) (n=414), Luxembourg (n=300), Berlin (Germany) (n=344), Perth (Australia) (n=300), and Oakland (USA) (n = 302) between 2003 and 2005, this study involved both pre- and post-intervention surveys around hydrogen bus projects to gauge changes in public perception. In Luxembourg, the acceptance of hydrogen buses is notably high. The study found that over 50% of respondents in Luxembourg indicated a willingness to pay an extra fee between 0.01 and 0.30 Euros per bus fare to support the implementation of hydrogen buses. Luxembourg's data showed that there is virtually no opposition to the introduction of hydrogen fuel technologies, with a strong curiosity about hydrogen-powered buses observed among the respondents.

“

Many people from Luxembourg are curious towards hydrogen powered buses. 25% of the respondents would – at least once – wait for a longer time to catch the hydrogen bus rather than the conventional one.

”

Source 30. Hydrogen acceptance in the transition phase (HYACINTH): Deliverable 5.2 - General findings on public acceptance

The HYACINTH project's deliverable D5.2 analyses public acceptance and awareness regarding hydrogen fuel cell (FCH) applications across seven European countries (Belgium, France, Germany, Norway, Slovenia, Spain, and the United Kingdom). The multi-country survey collected responses

from nationally representative samples of approximately 1000 adults from each country during April and May 2016. The survey results reveal that approximately 60% of respondents support FCH applications, while 30% remain neutral, and nearly 10% oppose them. Support is higher in Slovenia, Spain, and Germany, with lower levels observed in the United Kingdom, France, and Belgium.

Existing public preferences may become a hurdle to a hydrogen future. Understanding attitudes and behaviours provides insights into the factors that influence how individuals and households decide on electricity, heat, and transportation technologies. Along with other measures, European carbon targets should be underpinned by evaluating the likely role of public and customer preference and choice.

A – Austria, BE – Belgium, HR – Croatia, CZ- Czechia, DK – Denmark, EE – Estonia, FI – Finland, DE – Germany, HU – Hungary, IE – Ireland, IT – Italy, LV – Latvia, LT – Lithuania, LU – Luxembourg, NL – Netherlands, PL – Poland, PT – Portugal, RO – Romania, SK – Slovakia, SL – Slovenia, ES – Spain, EU27 – All EU countries

Figure 2: Studies according to the year conducted, location, and size of the study

Hydrogen public opinion results by valence

The literature summaries underwent sentiment analysis, revealing that most studies exhibited positive or mixed valences toward hydrogen (Table 3). Broadly positive opinions were noted, such as increased support for hydrogen technologies following participation in education programmes, a willingness to pay for hydrogen-powered vehicles, and a high percentage of support for hydrogen technologies overall. Mixed responses were also prevalent, indicating broad support for hydrogen technologies but often with caveats, such as support contingent on the technology sourced from renewable sources or concerns regarding safety and costs. Low support percentages primarily characterised negative perspectives compared to other green technologies; for example, one study found that only 20% of respondents would purchase a hydrogen-powered vehicle, contrasting with 60% preferring e-cars (#27).

Table 3. Hydrogen public opinion results by positive, mixed or negative valence

Hydrogen Public Opinion Results Valence	References with Findings in each Category
Positive	2, 4, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 15, 16, 17, 26, 29, 30
Mixed	1, 3, 5, 6, 7, 13, 14, 18, 22, 24, 25, 28
Negative	19, 20, 21, 23, 27

Notably, despite being classified as generally negative, the studies did not have strongly anti-hydrogen sentiments; concerns primarily revolved around safety, costs, and a lack of awareness about the technology. It is important to acknowledge that valence analysis is subjective, and it could be argued that all studies represent varying degrees of mixed responses to hydrogen.

2.3 Literature review conclusion

This collection of European studies presents a nuanced picture of public opinion regarding hydrogen technologies. For example, although there is significant support for hydrogen as a part of renewable energy initiatives in Latvia, there remains a notable gap in detailed understanding and public awareness. The pattern of favourable public opinion coupled with relatively low informational depth is reflected across several EU countries, including those with advanced hydrogen strategies like Germany and Poland. These findings imply a base of support for hydrogen technologies based on the perceived environmental benefits. Yet, support for hydrogen technologies may be contingent on increasing public awareness and addressing misconceptions about safety and applications.

Indeed, this evidence synthesis highlights the interrelated nature of knowledge, cultural predispositions, and societal acceptance. Findings from the Netherlands, for example, suggest a pattern where public support for hydrogen technologies does not necessarily correlate with a deep understanding of the technology itself. Instead, cultural predispositions such as environmental concern and trust in technology play a more definitive role. This is evidenced by studies indicating that individuals with a pre-existing trust in scientific and technological advancements are more likely to support hydrogen technology, even if their factual knowledge is limited. The Netherlands research

elucidates a pivotal finding: as knowledge about hydrogen increases, so does the influence of these cultural predispositions on individual support, suggesting an intertwined relationship between information dissemination and intrinsic values.

Overall, the European public's attitude towards hydrogen technologies is cautiously optimistic but highlights a clear need for strategic educational campaigns and transparent communication about the benefits and safety of hydrogen energy. This necessity is echoed in the research from Ireland, where safety and cost are pivotal to gaining public trust and acceptance for transitioning to hydrogen energy.

European attitudes towards hydrogen technology, especially in terms of its infrastructure and applications like hydrogen fuel cells and buses, exhibit general positivity but face challenges due to the NIMBY (Not in my backyard) phenomenon. This is particularly prominent in Germany, where while the populace may view hydrogen positively, local infrastructure projects such as pipelines meet with decreased acceptance. The volatility in public opinion is marked by a dynamic acceptance pattern, responsiveness to new information, and influence by ongoing communication strategies.

The broader European context shows a gradual increase in awareness and favourability towards hydrogen technologies, underpinned by their potential environmental benefits. Yet, this support is tempered by concerns related to infrastructure and the perceived risks associated with technology. The insights from Spain and Italy, where there is strong backing for hydrogen in public transport, contrast with the cautious approach seen in Germany and the Netherlands concerning hydrogen infrastructure in residential areas.

Despite differing stages of hydrogen technology integration within their respective energy strategies in Poland and Germany, public perception aligns with viewing hydrogen as environmentally friendly and innovative. However, perceptions of the technology's reliability and cost-effectiveness diverge, influenced by national contexts and the extent of governmental and infrastructural commitment to hydrogen. This dichotomy between the two nations reflects broader European trends where public enthusiasm for hydrogen energy is moderated by practical concerns about cost and infrastructure, as also seen in research in Denmark highlighting hesitance regarding hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEVs) due to high costs and inadequate refuelling infrastructure.

Public opinion research in the EU27 indicates a skew towards positive views. However, the existing published literature does not cover some countries, namely Malta, Cyprus, and Sweden. Fortunately, the dataset we analyse in the subsequent section includes these countries.

There are some examples of overlap in the data. For instance, studies #12 and #29 use the same data regarding the Accept H2 survey; however, they are written with a slightly different focus and come from various sources. Similarly, studies #25 and #28 appear to use the same survey data but analyse different aspects. The data comprised two reports, one master's thesis, two conference proceedings, and the rest are peer-reviewed journal articles. Most studies were opinion surveys; however, one survey (#15) was a willingness-to-pay study.

3 Secondary analysis on public perceptions and reactions to hydrogen

3.1 Secondary analysis methodology

This analysis draws on the same data as the Gallup International (2023) *Awareness of Hydrogen Technologies Survey Report*. The public opinion survey was launched to analyse and assess European citizens' attitudes towards and level of knowledge of hydrogen technologies and determine a baseline for monitoring changes in public opinion over time. The online survey research, with supplementary telephone interviews¹, was conducted in Autumn 2022, with a representative sample of 1000 citizens aged 15 years and above², in each EU Member State. The samples in all the countries were stratified by gender, age, administrative region, and type of locality³. The survey explored various issues, including knowledge and awareness of energy in general and of hydrogen energy in particular. The main objectives of the study were:

- To understand perceptions on the use of fuel cells and hydrogen (FCH) technologies in terms of:
 - Overall awareness, acceptance, and uptake of hydrogen technologies
 - Perceptions of the safety and sustainability of hydrogen technologies
- To create a benchmark metric that will be able to track changing perceptions in the European population over time
- To provide a basis for further analysis and recommendations

The report did not provide a detailed analysis of hydrogen attitudes disaggregated by country and gender. Here, we have conducted a deeper analysis of the data from this survey and present disaggregated country-level results regarding public perceptions of hydrogen technology by gender and age to provide a more complete picture of key patterns that could have implications for public engagement.

3.2 Secondary analysis results: Awareness and familiarity with hydrogen energy

In the survey, respondents were asked if they had 'seen, read or heard anything about hydrogen as an energy source' (Figure 2). The majority reported technology awareness but not familiarity, with 13,603 respondents (56%) indicating "Yes, but not at all familiar with it." Another 6,621 participants (27%) responded: "Yes, and rather familiar with it." A smaller group, 4,183 individuals (17%), stated, "No, never heard or read about it." Across all countries, there was a notable trend that more respondents had heard of hydrogen energy (Category 1 and 2 combined) than those who had never

¹ In total, 25,934 interviews were conducted with fieldwork taking place in Autumn 2022.

² A certain number of telephone interviews were conducted with citizens aged 65 years and above.

³ This stratification was designed using the following sociodemographic variables:

- Gender (Male, Female)
- Age (15-24, 25-39, 40-54, 55 years or more)
- Region: The widest geographical coverage of the population was sampled to ensure representativeness. All NUTS II regions were included in our survey.
- Urbanisation (rural area, small or mid size town, large city).

heard of it (Category 3). This suggested a relatively higher awareness of hydrogen energy among the surveyed population.

Figure 2. Technology Awareness: Hydrogen Energy (A02_4)

When looking at the "familiar" (Category 1) with "heard but not familiar" (Category 2), the data varies by country. Some countries showed a higher percentage of respondents familiar with hydrogen energy. Most respondents across most countries have heard of hydrogen energy but are not familiar with it (Category 2), often constituting over 50% of responses, which indicated a general awareness of hydrogen energy but a lack of in-depth knowledge. Notable is that in nearly all countries, females slightly lead in this category.

Individuals who have never heard of hydrogen energy (Category 3) comprised the smallest group in almost all countries, indicating that while hydrogen energy was not widely understood, there was at least some awareness.

3.2.1 Hydrogen energy familiarity by country and gender

Familiarity with hydrogen energy (Category 1)

Trends across countries showed similar patterns (Figure 3). For example, most of the male respondents in Slovakia (67%) reported being familiar with hydrogen energy, which was the highest familiarity rate observed. Other countries had higher percentages of familiarity among men including Luxembourg (51%), Poland (45%), Malta (44%), Germany (43%), Cyprus (40%), and Bulgaria (40%).

Figure 3. Familiar with Hydrogen Energy (A02_4; Category 1, Gender by Country)

Heard of but not familiar with hydrogen energy (Category 2)

Women generally led in Category 2, signifying awareness without detailed knowledge (Figure 4). For example, in Portugal (73%), most female respondents indicated hearing about the hydrogen but not being familiar with it. This suggests that while women are nearly as aware as men of hydrogen as an energy source.

Figure 4. Heard but unfamiliar with hydrogen energy (A02_4; Category 2, Gender by Country)

Neither heard of nor familiar with hydrogen energy (Category 3)

Several countries displayed substantial disparities in gender responses, especially in Category 3 (Figure 5). Females are overrepresented in this category compared to males.

Figure 5. Neither heard nor familiar with hydrogen energy (A02_4; Category 3, Gender by Country)

Hydrogen energy familiarity with mean scores by country and gender

Mean scores were created based on a point value for each response (Figure 6), where 1 = "Yes, and rather familiar with it.", 2 = "Yes, but not at all familiar with it.", 3 = "No, never heard or read about it." Higher mean scores indicated less awareness/familiarity with hydrogen energy. These mean scores aim to provide a numerical insight into the overall familiarity level across genders: in all countries, higher mean scores are indicated for females than males.

Figure 6. Means of Heard or Familiar with Hydrogen Energy (A02_4; All Categories, Gender by Country)

3.2.2 Hydrogen energy familiarity by country and age

Familiarity with hydrogen energy (Category 1)

Across all age brackets (Figure 7), Slovakia stands out with the highest awareness/familiarity with hydrogen energy. Other countries, including Luxembourg, Poland, Malta, Italy, Germany, Greece, and Bulgaria, also had high percentages of familiarity across age brackets. Younger groups (15-24) in countries such as Slovakia, Italy, and Romania showed a high percentage of familiarity compared to their counterparts in countries such as Portugal where the familiarity is notably lower.

Figure 7. Familiar with Hydrogen Energy (A02_4; Category 1, Age by Country)

Heard but not familiar with hydrogen energy (Category 2)

There was variation across age groups in Category 2 (Figure 8). Here, Portugal was notably high in awareness while Cyprus was at the other extreme.

Figure 8. Heard but unfamiliar with hydrogen energy (A02_4; Category 2, Age by Country)

Neither heard nor familiar with hydrogen energy (Category 3)

The overall trend across most countries indicated a lack of awareness/familiarity with hydrogen energy (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Neither heard nor familiar with hydrogen energy (A02_4; Category 3, Age by Country)

Southern Europe displayed varied trends. Cyprus, among the EU13, was the country with the highest rates of unawareness/unfamiliarity across all ages, which started at 30% in the 15-24 age group and peaked at 68% in the 65 and above age group. In contrast, Malta, also among the EU13, showed an overall decline in unawareness/unfamiliarity from 28% in the youngest age group to a low of 11% in the oldest age group. Greece and Italy maintained moderate unawareness/unfamiliarity across all age groups, with Greece peaking at 25% in the oldest age group.

In Northern European countries, Denmark had the highest levels, peaking at 43% among those aged 65 and above. Sweden demonstrated a decreasing trend with age, notably dropping to 15% in the oldest age group. Countries such as Austria, Germany, and the Netherlands had relatively low levels of unawareness/unfamiliarity across all age groups, with particularly low figures in the oldest age group. Luxembourg and Belgium, for example, had more varied percentages but generally showed lower unawareness/unfamiliarity in the younger age groups, with slight increases or stable trends as age increased.

Hydrogen energy familiarity with mean scores by country and age

Mean scores were created based on a point value for each response (Figure 10), where 1 = "Yes, and rather familiar with it.", 2 = "Yes, but not at all familiar with it.", 3 = "No, never heard or read about it." Higher mean scores indicated less awareness/familiarity with hydrogen energy (Figure 15). The data shows that familiarity does not drastically change with age in most countries.

Figure 10. Means of awareness/familiarity with hydrogen energy (A02_4; All Categories, Age by Country)

3.3 Secondary analysis results: Views of hydrogen energy and technologies

Respondents were asked to answer this question, “To what extent do you agree or disagree with each of the following statements regarding Hydrogen energy and technologies?”, with four subsequent statements regarding its ability to reduce energy dependence⁴ and its potential as a sustainable⁵, safe⁶, and clean⁷ energy source. Across these items, there was a general trend towards positive perceptions of hydrogen.

3.3.1 Views on hydrogen as a solution for energy dependence

Trends by Country

Respondents were asked about their views of hydrogen as a ‘good solution for reducing the energy dependence of their country’. The descriptive statistics reveal varying levels of agreement across different European countries (Figure 11). The data highlighted mostly positive views and broad acceptance of hydrogen as a potential energy solution across most of the sampled countries, with most recording over 80% agreement (combined ‘totally agree’ and ‘tend to agree’ categories), and even the “lowest performing countries” recording levels of overall agreement above 70%.

Notably, Portugal had the highest overall agreement, with 91% of respondents viewing hydrogen as a good solution for reducing energy dependence. Closely behind, Italy (89%) and Poland (88%) showed similarly strong positive responses. Ireland (87%), Denmark (85%), and Greece (86%) also showed amongst the highest levels of ‘tend to agree’ responses. In contrast, the countries with the lowest levels of agreement were observed in Latvia (72%), Estonia (74%), and Sweden (73%). Latvia and Estonia, EU13 countries, appeared consistent in the Baltic states, while Sweden was an outlier among Scandinavian states.

⁴ Energy Dependence (B07_2): “Hydrogen is a good solution for reducing the energy dependence of [Country].”

⁵ Sustainable Energy (B07_3): “Hydrogen is a sustainable energy source.”

⁶ Safety (B07_6): “The use of Hydrogen is as safe as the use of any other energy source.”

⁷ Polluting (B07_5): “Hydrogen is as polluting as Diesel or gasoline.”

Figure 11. Levels of agreement about energy dependence (B07_2; All Categories by Country)

Support for the view that hydrogen reduces energy dependence by gender

The data provided a breakdown of views across countries on whether 'hydrogen is a good solution for reducing the energy dependence' of their respective countries (Figure 12). Responses were categorised into 'Totally agree' and 'Tend to agree', with separate statistics for males and females.

Most countries had a general trend of high agreement (above 70%), with very few countries showing less than 75% agreement in either gender. The female demographic in many countries showed a higher overall propensity to support hydrogen, aligning with the broader trend observed in the data.

Figure 12. Levels of agreement about reducing energy dependence (B07_2; All Categories, Country and Gender)

In nearly every country, females were slightly more likely to ‘Tend to agree’ than males, which indicated a gender difference in the positive views about hydrogen as an energy solution. Females in countries like Finland, Cyprus, Hungary, Ireland, Greece, Netherlands, and Belgium agreed more with the statement in the ‘Tend to agree’ category than males. Countries like Latvia and Estonia showed the lowest overall agreement among both genders, but females tended to agree more than males.

Opposition to the view that hydrogen reduces energy dependence by gender

Across the countries, disagreement (combining “Tend to disagree” and “Totally disagree”) tended to be much lower than the previously discussed agreement levels regarding hydrogen’s contribution to reducing energy dependence (Figure 13). Many countries, such as Sweden, Slovenia, and Czechia, showed similar disagreement rates between genders, with slight variations.

Figure 13. Levels of disagreement about reducing energy dependence (B07_2; All Categories, Country, and Gender)

In countries like Spain and Bulgaria, females disagreed that hydrogen would reduce energy dependence more than males. Notably higher levels of negative views among both genders were observed in Latvia (30% male, 27% female) and Estonia (28% male, 23% female). The lowest levels of negative views were observed in Portugal, Italy, and Poland between both genders, where ‘total disagreement’ was around 10%.

3.3.2 Views on hydrogen as a sustainable energy source

Trends by Country

The descriptive statistics reveal varying levels of agreement across European countries (Figure 14). There was a pronounced trend towards positive views that hydrogen is a sustainable energy source across most of the sampled countries, with 84% in agreement (combined totally agree and tend to agree categories).

Results showed that Portugal and Malta (EU13) had the highest levels of agreement on hydrogen sustainability, with 92% of respondents in each country supporting the statement, followed by Italy (90%). Conversely, EU13 countries Estonia (75%) and Slovenia (74%) reported the lowest agreement, albeit still relatively high. The remaining countries showed varied levels of agreement, generally aligning within the 79% to 86% range, indicating diverse perceptions of hydrogen’s sustainability across Europe.

Figure 14. Levels of agreement about hydrogen as a sustainable energy source (B07_3; All Categories by Country)

Support for the view that hydrogen is sustainable by gender

The data on hydrogen sustainability views highlighted distinct trends in positive views between genders across various European countries, revealing both close similarities and notable disparities in certain cases (Figure 15). Notably, the trend of higher prevalence in female support was consistent across several countries, with women generally expressing slightly higher or equal support than men, except in a few instances like Italy, Spain, and Luxembourg, where support among males was higher.

Figure 15. Support for views of hydrogen as a sustainable energy source (B07_3; All Categories, Country, and Gender)

Portugal reported the highest agreement regarding hydrogen sustainability among males (93%) and females (91%). Malta (EU13), however, showed the highest female support (93%) compared to males (91%). There was a pattern of higher male support in countries like Italy (92% male, 88% female) and Spain (84% male, 83% female). Conversely, females showed higher support than males in EU13 countries such as Hungary (83% male, 85% female) and Estonia (73% male, 77% female).

The smallest gender disparity within countries was observed in Poland (88%), Slovakia (79%) and Denmark (82%), where both genders reported the same levels of support. Sweden (77% male, 71% female) and Slovenia (75% male, 73% female) showed larger gender differences, with males showing more overall support than females. EU13 countries such as Slovenia and Estonia had some of the lowest overall support among both genders, although still relatively high.

Opposition to the view that hydrogen is sustainable by gender

The data also reflected negative views of the statement "Hydrogen is a sustainable energy source" across countries, segmented by male and female responses (Figure 16). Notably, the general trend indicated negative views were below 30% for both genders.

Figure 16. Opposition to the view that hydrogen is a sustainable energy source (B07_3; All Categories, Country, and Gender)

In most countries, male opposition was equal to or greater than female opposition, with notable exceptions in Sweden (23% male, 29% female) and Slovenia (23% male, 29% female) where females exceeded males. Estonia reported the highest level of opposition among males (27%) compared to females (23%). Countries such as Slovakia (21%), Denmark (18%), and Poland (12%) had equal opposition among both genders.

Malta and Italy had the lowest opposition for both genders. Malta (9% female, 9% male) had the lowest level, and Italy (8% male, 12% female) had a similarly low level. In EU13 countries such as Lithuania, Latvia, Czechia, and Bulgaria, opposition to hydrogen as a sustainable energy source was generally low (below 20% for both genders).

3.3.3 Views on hydrogen as a safe energy source

Trends by Country

The descriptive statistics reveal varying levels of agreement across European countries (Figure 17). The data highlighted acceptance of hydrogen as a safe energy source across most of the sampled countries; however, most countries recorded less than 80% agreement (combined ‘totally agree’ and ‘tend to agree’ categories).

Portugal (86%) displayed the highest agreement, followed by Ireland (83%), Italy (82%), Poland (81%), Spain (81%), Romania (80%) and Malta (80%) as the countries above 80% overall agreement. The percentages gradually decreased across other countries. In contrast, the agreement levels were notably lower in some Baltic and Eastern European countries. For instance, Czechia, Slovakia, and Bulgaria each recorded an agreement level of 65%. The lowest agreement levels were observed in Latvia (61%).

Notable trends include a general west-to-east gradient, where Western European countries showed higher agreement levels with hydrogen safety than their Eastern counterparts.

Figure 17. Levels of agreement about hydrogen safety (B07_6; All Categories by Country)

Support for the view that hydrogen is safe by gender

The data provided the positive views of male and female respondents in various countries who

agreed with the statement, "The use of Hydrogen is as safe as the use of any other energy source." (Figure 18). The data indicated consistent gender-specific support for hydrogen safety as an energy source in most countries.

Figure 18. Support for the view that hydrogen is safe (B07_6; All Categories, Country, and Gender)

Some countries showed strong support for hydrogen safety among both genders including Portugal (86% male and female), Italy (83% male, 80% female), and Spain (83% male, 78% female). EU13 countries such as Slovenia (64% male and female), Estonia (64% male and female), and Latvia (59% male, 62% female) displayed the lowest support among both genders. In Lithuania (EU13), support among females (75%) was notably higher than males (62%).

Opposition to the view that hydrogen is safe by gender

The data showed the negative views of male respondents across various European countries who disagreed with the statement, "The use of Hydrogen is as safe as the use of any other energy source" (Figure 19). Across all countries, males and females displayed relatively low opposition, generally not exceeding 41% for males and 38% for females.

Figure 19. Opposition to the view that hydrogen is safe (B07_6; All Categories, Country and Gender)

Latvia had the highest opposition among males (41%) and females (38%). Whereas, Portugal (14% males and females), Italy (17% males, 20% females), and Spain (17% males, 22% females) had the lowest opposition. Lithuania showed a large gender difference in opposition between males (38%) and females (25%). Both genders had identical opposition rates (36%) in Slovenia and Estonia. Ireland

showed one of the most substantial disparities between male (20%) and female (12%) opposition levels.

3.3.4 Views on hydrogen as a polluting energy source similar to fossil fuels

Trends by Country

The data showed positive views that hydrogen was a less polluting energy source across most of the sampled countries, indicating a broad perception that hydrogen can be a cleaner alternative to traditional fossil fuels (Figure 20).

Finland (81%) had the highest percentage of disagreement (pro-hydrogen) on this reverse-coded statement, followed by EU13 countries Bulgaria (79%) and Malta (78%). Conversely, Greece (67%) and Austria (69%) had the lowest levels of disagreement (pro-hydrogen). Countries like Denmark (75%), Germany (76%), and the Netherlands (70%) often recognised for their pro-environmental policies, reported a mid-range of disagreement (pro-hydrogen), aligning them closely with the overall trend of positive responses to hydrogen’s lesser pollution impact.

Figure 20. Levels of agreement about hydrogen pollution (B07_5; All Categories by Country)

Opposition to the view that hydrogen is polluting by gender

These data indicated that most countries surveyed tended to show higher hydrogen support (by disagreeing with the statement, 'Hydrogen is as polluting as Diesel or gasoline') among male respondents than female respondents (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Opposition to the view that hydrogen is polluting (B07_5; All Categories, Gender, and Country)

Cyprus (83% male, 65% female) showed a substantial gender difference in support, with males showing 18% higher support than females. Malta (85% male, 71% female) also displayed a notable gender gap, with males 14% higher. France (71% male, 62% female) and Croatia (78% male, 70% female) showed around 9% difference. Less of a gender difference was noted in countries like Portugal (82% male, 79% female), Estonia (77% male, 73% female), and Italy (71% male, 69% female), which ranged from 4% to 1%,

Support for the view that hydrogen is polluting by gender

The descriptive statistics revealed varying levels of overall opposition across European countries, as measured on a reverse-coded Likert-type scale (Figure 22). The data suggests a mixed perception across Europe, with some trends indicating higher scepticism or concern about hydrogen in specific regions.

Figure 22. Support for the view that hydrogen is polluting (B07_5; All Categories, Gender, and Country)

Cyprus showed the largest gender disparity, with 35% of females and 17% of males in opposition. High levels of female opposition were noted in France (38%) and Sweden (36%), while the male opposition stood at 29% in both countries. Moderate opposition was seen in Italy (30% both male and female), Belgium (27% male, 29% female) and Spain (26% male, 29% female), where both genders showed similar opposition levels. Generally, female respondents opposed the statement slightly more than male respondents that hydrogen was as polluting as diesel or gasoline. This trend was uniform across almost all countries, except for Portugal (30% male, 27% female), Germany (27% male, 25% female), and a few other countries with very small (1%) differences.

4 Conclusions and implications for public engagement

The EU27 public perception of hydrogen technology is characterised by differences in knowledge, cultural predispositions, and societal acceptance, influenced by regional and national factors and overarching EU-wide trends. There is a consistent theme of support for hydrogen technology that is often not underpinned by deep understanding and familiarity with this topic. Relevant research evidence indicates that factors such as environmental concern and trust in scientific advancements may significantly shape these attitudes. The research also points to the critical role of cultural predispositions, which strengthen with increased knowledge and heavily influence acceptance as understanding grows.

At a broader level, while there is general positivity towards hydrogen technology across the EU27, this support often encounters hurdles when implementing related infrastructure, particularly in residential areas. The literature review points to examples of this in Germany, where public approval for hydrogen is otherwise very high. Yet, local projects like hydrogen pipelines face resistance due to the NIMBY phenomenon. Similar challenges are seen in Denmark and Poland, where enthusiasm for hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEVs) and other applications has been tempered by cost, infrastructure, and safety concerns. These insights suggest that support for hydrogen technology is conditional, requiring targeted communication strategies to address safety concerns and infrastructural issues.

Our analysis shows that the perception of hydrogen technology varies considerably across Europe, reflecting distinct national attitudes and contexts. Differences between and within countries in levels of awareness and familiarity highlight the need for localised educational campaigns sensitive to each country's unique cultural, environmental, and political landscape. Regarding the environmental and safety perceptions of hydrogen, the overall sentiment across Europe is positive, with a strong majority viewing hydrogen as a sustainable and safer alternative to traditional fossil fuels.

Ultimately EU13 countries evinced a broad range of views about hydrogen technology, sometimes more supportive than the EU27 and sometimes less. In EU13 nations such as Bulgaria and Malta, there is a strong belief in hydrogen's environmental benefits. At the same time, scepticism about its safety persists in some EU13 countries such as Czechia, Slovakia, and Bulgaria due to variable trust in new technologies and regulatory frameworks.

To shift address these perceptions, it is imperative to establish and communicate strict safety standards and the environmental benefits of hydrogen effectively.

Implications for public engagement

Our analysis shows that public awareness of hydrogen technology across the EU27 tends to be high, yet it is underpinned by only a superficial awareness of hydrogen as an energy source. That is, while over 80% of European respondents have some level of hydrogen awareness, in-depth understanding remains limited. This broad but shallow awareness could form a robust base for targeted educational initiatives to deepen knowledge and correct misconceptions. Men generally claim greater familiarity with hydrogen technology. This gender-specific disparity in familiarity indicates the need for communication strategies tailored to address the diverse informational needs of various

demographic groups. It may also link to broader patterns of underrepresentation of women in STEM professions.

Enhancing public acceptance and support for hydrogen technology in Europe necessitates a multifaceted approach that integrates continuous, effective information dissemination with robust, trust-building communication strategies. Showcasing successful hydrogen implementations can also transform general awareness into well-informed support, thus facilitating Europe's transition towards a hydrogen-enhanced energy future and a broader shift towards improved inclusion of women in STEM. This approach should clarify the benefits and safety of hydrogen technology and tackle the infrastructural and economic concerns that inhibit broader acceptance. Emphasising the environmental advantages while transparently addressing practical and safety issues could foster a more informed and supportive public, pivotal for advancing hydrogen technology as a cornerstone of Europe's energy transition and decarbonisation efforts. This strategy aligns with findings from across the EU27, where the path to acceptance is paved with informed public engagement and policy-driven support.

5 Appendix A. Secondary analysis methodology

This section contains supplemental methodological details produced as part of IMI’s analysis.

1. Gender distribution across all countries

Across all countries, there is a relatively even distribution between male and female respondents, with slight percentage variations (Figure 23). Female respondents numbered 12,286, accounting for 50% of the total, and male respondents also constituted 50% with a count of 12,121.

Figure 23. Gender distribution across all countries

2. Hydrogen familiarity response distribution by gender

Men tended to have a higher rate of responses in Category 1, indicating that they were more familiar with hydrogen compared to women (Figure 24.). Similar percentages across all countries fell into Category 2 between men and women. More females than males stated they had never heard of hydrogen energy across all countries (Category 3).

Figure 24. Awareness and Familiarity with Hydrogen Energy (A02_4; All Categories distributed by Gender)

1. Age distribution across all countries

Across all countries, there was a relatively even distribution between age groups of respondents, with slight variations in percentages (Figure 25). The 40-54 age bracket represented the largest group (n=6173, 25%), which was closely followed by the 25-39 age bracket (n=5831, 24%), and individuals aged 65 and above (n=5359, 22%). Those in the 55-64 age group made up 16% of the total (n=3907), while the 15-24 category accounted for 13% (n=3200).

Figure 25. Age distribution across all countries

2. Hydrogen familiarity response distribution by age

All age groups had similar and closely comparable rates of responses across categories (Figure 26), with the highest rate of responses in Category 2. Smaller percentages were evident in Category 3, with only minor deviations in respondents stating they had never heard of hydrogen energy. While younger age groups tended to be more familiar, older individuals showed less familiarity despite having heard of the subject. Overall, most respondents across all countries heard of the topic but were not entirely familiar with it.

Figure 26. Awareness and Familiarity with Hydrogen Energy (A02_4; All Categories distributed by Age)

B07. To what extent do you agree or disagree with each of the following statements regarding Hydrogen energy and technologies?

Across these items, there was a general trend towards positive perceptions of hydrogen regarding its sustainability, safety, and potential to reduce energy dependence. Similarly, there was a pronounced trend towards positive views that hydrogen is a sustainable energy source⁸, with a total of 84% in agreement. Also, most perceived hydrogen as safe, with 74% of respondents agreeing that hydrogen was as safe as other energy sources⁹. A majority disagreed with the statement that hydrogen is as polluting as diesel or gasoline¹⁰, with 74% indicating a positive perception of hydrogen as being less polluting than traditional fossil fuels.

B07.2. Hydrogen is a good solution for reducing the energy dependence of [Country]

Respondents were asked about their views of hydrogen as a good solution for reducing the energy dependence of their country (Figure 27). The data showed a strong inclination towards positive

⁸ Sustainable Energy (B07_3)

⁹ Safety (B07_6)

¹⁰ Polluting (B07_5)

views, with 82% of respondents agreeing that hydrogen is a good solution for reducing energy dependence¹¹. As an indication of positive views, most tended to agree (n=11386, 55%) and totally agree (n=5580, 27%) with the statement. Alternatively, negative views were indicated by a small proportion that tended to disagree (n=2822, 14%) or totally disagree (n=828, 4%).

Figure 27. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Reducing Energy Dependence (B07_2; All Categories)

B07.3. Hydrogen is a sustainable energy source

Respondents were asked about their views of hydrogen as a sustainable energy source (Figure 28). Most respondents ‘tended to agree’ (n=11117, 56%) and ‘totally agreed’ (n=5559, 28%), indicating positive views about hydrogen sustainability. Negative views were not widely held, as indicated by only 13% who ‘tended to disagree’ (n=2547) and 3% who ‘totally disagreed’ (n=660).

Figure 28. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Increasing Sustainability (B07_3; All Categories)

B07.6. The use of Hydrogen is as safe as the use of any other energy source

Respondents were asked about hydrogen's safety compared to other energy sources (Figure 29). In the assessment, a majority ‘tended to agree’ (n=9685, 52%) or ‘totally agreed’ (n=4137, 22%) that Hydrogen was perceived as safe. Conversely, a minority ‘tended to disagree’ (n=3954, 21%) and ‘totally disagreed’ (n=985, 5%) with the statement, indicating that Hydrogen may not have comparable safety with other energy sources.

¹¹ Energy Dependence (B07_2)

Figure 29. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Safety (B07_6; All Categories)

B07.5. Hydrogen is as polluting as Diesel or gasoline.

Respondents were asked whether hydrogen was ‘as polluting as diesel or gasoline’ (Figure 30). Views were divided, but most ‘tended to disagree’ (n=7305, 38%) or ‘totally disagreed’ (n=7087, 36%), indicating they did not see Hydrogen as polluting. Indeed, only a minority either ‘tended to agree’ (n=3515, 18%) or ‘totally agreed’ (n=1516, 8%), indicating a negative view of hydrogen as equivalent to fossil fuels.

Figure 30. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Polluting (B07_5; All Categories)

The role of gender in views towards Hydrogen energy and technologies (B07)

The data showed a consistent pattern where most respondents, irrespective of gender, agreed on the positive aspects of hydrogen as an energy solution regarding dependence, sustainability, environmental impact, and safety (Figure 31). The descriptive statistics provided for the hydrogen energy and technologies survey show response distributions and means categorised by gender and aggregated across all respondents. The sample distribution for the hydrogen energy and technologies survey included a higher proportion of male respondents than female respondents across all statements.

Figure 31. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Energy (B07; All Categories, Gender)

1. Energy Dependence (B07.2)

The total number of respondents was 20616, with males (10908, 53%) and females (9708, 47%). The combined mean score across all respondents was 1.47, indicating a general lean towards agreement in the belief that hydrogen is a good solution for reducing energy dependence.

2. Sustainability (B07.3):

A slightly smaller total respondent count of 19833 featured a gender distribution of more males (10682, 54%) and females (9151, 46%). The overall mean score was similarly low at 1.46, reflecting a consensus towards agreeing that hydrogen is a sustainable energy source.

3. Polluting Compared to Diesel or Gasoline (B07.5):

This statement involved 19373 participants, with males constituting 55% (10592) and females 45% (8,781). The mean score was 1.45, which, like the other categories, shows a trend towards disagreement with the statement that hydrogen is as polluting as diesel or gasoline, suggesting a positive view of hydrogen's environmental impact.

4. Safety (B07.6):

The number of respondents for the safety question totalled 18716, again with a distribution of 55% male (10346) and 45% female (8370). The mean score here was also 1.45, indicating general agreement that hydrogen use is as safe as other energy sources.

B07.2. Hydrogen is a good solution for reducing the energy dependence of [Country]

Regarding whether hydrogen is a good solution for reducing the energy dependence in the respondents' country (Figure 32). A majority of respondents showed agreement, with 82% either 'totally' or 'tending to agree'. Analysing by gender, males and females showed similar levels of agreement overall, although a slightly higher percentage of females (59%) 'tended to agree' compared to males (52%). Across the board, more respondents 'Tended to agree' than those who 'Totally agreed' that hydrogen was a viable solution.

Figure 32. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen’s Contribution to Energy Dependence (B07_2; All Categories, Gender)

B07.3. Hydrogen is a sustainable energy source

Regarding the view of Hydrogen as a sustainable energy source, males (83%) and females (84%) were similar in overall agreement (Figure 33). However, there was a noticeable difference in the proportion of females who ‘tend to agree’ (60%) compared to males (52%), while more males (31%) indicated they ‘totally agree’ with hydrogen's sustainability than females (24%).

Figure 33. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen as a Sustainable Energy Sources (B07_3; All Categories)

B07.6. The use of Hydrogen is as safe as the use of any other energy source

Regarding hydrogen safety, the agreement distribution was fairly consistent between genders (Figure 34), with females (75%) showing a slightly higher agreement than males (73%). Males showed a slightly higher percentage of ‘total agreement’ (24%) than females (20%). The views on safety showed females (55%) ‘tended to agree’ slightly more than males (49%) that hydrogen was as safe as other energy sources.

Figure 34. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Safety (B07_6; All Categories, Gender)

B07.5. Hydrogen is as polluting as Diesel or gasoline

For the statement "Hydrogen is as polluting as Diesel or gasoline" (reverse coded), the majority of both males (76%) and females (72%) disagreed with this statement, which indicated a positive view of hydrogen's environmental impact, with either 'tending to' or 'totally disagreeing' (Figure 35). Males (43%) disagreed slightly more strongly with the statement than females (29%). Alternatively, a higher percentage of females (44%) 'tended to disagree' with the statement than males (33%).

Figure 35. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Pollution (B07_5; All Categories, Gender)

6 Appendix B. Secondary analysis tables

This section contains supplemental details produced as part of IMI's original analysis of the dataset collected by Gallup.

2.1 Overall Awareness Levels

The provided data table reveals how individuals in various countries have responded to a question about their awareness of hydrogen. The data is stratified by gender and summarised into three categories of awareness: 1) Yes, rather familiar with it; 2) Yes, but not at all familiar with it; and 3) No, never heard or read about it.

A02. Have you seen, read or heard anything about each of the following energy sources?

Table 4. Negative Views of Hydrogen Pollution Similar to Fossil Fuels (A02_4)

A02_4 Hydrogen		N	%
Yes, and you are rather familiar with it	1	6621	27%
Yes, but you are not at all familiar with it	2	13603	56%
No, you have never heard or read about it	3	4183	17%
Grand Total		24407	100%

Table 5. Gender of respondents for Heard and Familiar with Hydrogen Energy (A02_4)

Gender (D03)		N	%
Male	1	12121	50%
Female	2	12286	50%
Grand Total		24407	100%

Table 6. Age of respondents for Heard and Familiar with Hydrogen Energy (A02_4)

Age (D02A)		N	%
15-24	1	3200	13%
25-39	2	5831	24%
40-54	3	6173	25%
55-64	4	3907	16%
65 and above	5	5359	22%
Grand Total		24470	100%

Table 7. Country of respondents for Heard and Familiar with Hydrogen Energy (A02_4)

Country (A02_4)		N	%	\bar{x}
Belgium	56	1,014	4.15%	1.94
Portugal	620	1,000	4.10%	1.95
Spain	724	994	4.07%	1.96
Austria	40	978	4.01%	1.76
Germany	276	978	4.01%	1.70

Netherlands	528	975	3.99%	1.81
Italy	380	972	3.98%	1.72
Bulgaria	100	969	3.97%	1.78
Ireland	372	964	3.95%	2.01
Slovenia	705	964	3.95%	1.94
Croatia	191	959	3.93%	1.91
Greece	300	958	3.93%	1.88
Poland	616	959	3.93%	1.73
Estonia	233	955	3.91%	2.06
Hungary	348	954	3.91%	2.00
Romania	642	950	3.89%	1.82
France	250	947	3.88%	1.89
Finland	246	943	3.86%	1.94
Slovakia	703	939	3.85%	1.58
Czechia	203	922	3.78%	2.09
Latvia	428	922	3.78%	2.07
Sweden	752	921	3.77%	2.00
Denmark	208	915	3.75%	2.08
Lithuania	440	910	3.73%	2.03
Malta	470	493	2.02%	1.87
Luxembourg	442	484	1.98%	1.75
Cyprus	196	468	1.92%	2.06
Grand Total		24,407	100%	1.90

Table 8. Heard and Familiar with Hydrogen Energy (A02_4)

D03 Gender	Male		Female		Grand Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Finland	160	73%	59	27%	219	100%
Czechia	101	73%	38	27%	139	100%
Malta	114	72%	45	28%	159	100%
Slovenia	149	70%	65	30%	214	100%
France	171	69%	77	31%	248	100%
Estonia	103	68%	48	32%	151	100%
Denmark	149	68%	70	32%	219	100%
Greece	229	68%	110	32%	339	100%
Ireland	132	67%	65	33%	197	100%
Sweden	121	67%	60	33%	181	100%
Hungary	123	66%	62	34%	185	100%
Croatia	159	65%	85	35%	244	100%
Luxembourg	126	65%	69	35%	195	100%
Portugal	108	64%	60	36%	168	100%

Netherlands	173	64%	97	36%	270	100%
Belgium	142	63%	82	37%	224	100%
Slovakia	310	63%	186	38%	496	100%
Latvia	101	61%	64	39%	165	100%
Lithuania	111	60%	73	40%	184	100%
Cyprus	92	59%	64	41%	156	100%
Spain	122	59%	86	41%	208	100%
Romania	174	58%	125	42%	299	100%
Germany	210	58%	151	42%	361	100%
Austria	185	58%	135	42%	320	100%
Italy	210	57%	159	43%	369	100%
Bulgaria	190	56%	147	44%	337	100%
Poland	207	55%	167	45%	374	100%
Grand Total	4172	63%	2449	37%	6621	100%

Table 9. Heard and Familiar with Hydrogen Energy (A02_4; All Categories by Gender)

A02_4	D03 Gender			Female			Grand Total		
	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}
Yes, and rather familiar with it	4172	17%		2449	10%		6621	27%	
Yes, but not at all familiar with it	6615	27%		6988	29%		13603	56%	
No, never heard or read about it	1334	5%		2849	12%		4183	17%	
Grand Total	12121	50%	1.77	12286	50%	2.03	24407	100%	1.90

Table 10. Heard and Familiar with Hydrogen Energy (A02_4; All Categories by Age)

D02A Age	15-24			25-39			40-54			55-64			65 and above			Grand Total		
A02_4	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}									
Heard and familiar	1046	33%		1688	29%		1586	26%		1002	26%		1319	25%		6641	27%	
Heard but not at all familiar	1547	48%		3110	53%		3505	57%		2306	59%		3165	59%		13633	56%	
Never heard and not familiar	607	19%		1033	18%		1082	18%		599	15%		875	16%		4196	17%	
Grand Total	3200	13%	1.86	5831	24%	1.89	6173	25%	1.92	3907	16%	1.90	5359	22%	1.92	24470	100%	1.90

Table 11. Heard and Familiar with Hydrogen Energy (A02_4; All Categories by Gender and Country)

COUNTRY	CODE	A02_4	D03 Gender			Female			Grand Total		
			N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}
Austria	40	Yes, and rather familiar with it	185	39%		135	27%		320	33%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	260	55%		314	62%		574	59%	
		No, never heard or read about it	29	6%		55	11%		84	9%	
	40 Total	474	100%	1.67	504	100%	1.84	978	100%	1.76	
Belgium	56	Yes, and rather familiar with it	142	28%		82	16%		224	22%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	305	61%		325	63%		630	62%	
		No, never heard or read about it	52	10%		108	21%		160	16%	
	56 Total	499	100%	1.82	515	100%	2.05	1014	100%	1.94	
Bulgaria	100	Yes, and rather familiar with it	190	40%		147	30%		337	35%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	242	51%		264	53%		506	52%	
		No, never heard or read about it	42	9%		84	17%		126	13%	
	100 Total	474	100%	1.69	495	100%	1.87	969	100%	1.78	
Croatia	191	Yes, and rather familiar with it	159	33%		85	18%		244	25%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	274	57%		283	59%		557	58%	
		No, never heard or read about it	49	10%		109	23%		158	16%	
	191 Total	482	100%	1.77	477	100%	2.05	959	100%	1.91	
Cyprus	196	Yes, and rather familiar with it	92	40%		64	27%		156	33%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	63	27%		65	27%		128	27%	
		No, never heard or read about it	76	33%		108	46%		184	39%	
	196 Total	231	100%	1.93	237	100%	2.19	468	100%	2.06	
Czechia	203	Yes, and rather familiar with it	101	22%		38	8%		139	15%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	306	66%		259	57%		565	61%	
		No, never heard or read about it	60	13%		158	35%		218	24%	
	203 Total	467	100%	1.91	455	100%	2.26	922	100%	2.09	
Denmark	208	Yes, and rather familiar with it	149	32%		70	16%		219	24%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	217	46%		189	42%		406	44%	
		No, never heard or read about it	103	22%		187	42%		290	32%	
	208 Total	469	100%	1.90	446	100%	2.26	915	100%	2.08	
Estonia	233	Yes, and rather familiar with it	103	22%		48	10%		151	16%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	297	65%		299	60%		596	62%	
		No, never heard or read about it	60	13%		148	30%		208	22%	
	233 Total	460	100%	1.91	495	100%	2.20	955	100%	2.06	
Finland	246	Yes, and rather familiar with it	160	34%		59	13%		219	23%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	264	56%		293	62%		557	59%	
		No, never heard or read about it	47	10%		120	25%		167	18%	
	246 Total	471	100%	1.76	472	100%	2.13	943	100%	1.94	
France	250	Yes, and rather familiar with it	171	37%		77	16%		248	26%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	250	54%		304	63%		554	59%	
		No, never heard or read about it	41	9%		104	21%		145	15%	
	250 Total	462	100%	1.72	485	100%	2.06	947	100%	1.89	
Germany	276	Yes, and rather familiar with it	210	43%		151	31%		361	37%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	244	50%		302	61%		546	56%	

		No, never heard or read about it	31	6%		40	8%		71	7%	
		276 Total	485	100%	1.63	493	100%	1.77	978	100%	1.70
Greece	300	Yes, and rather familiar with it	229	46%		110	24%		339	35%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	210	42%		189	41%		399	42%	
		No, never heard or read about it	63	13%		157	34%		220	23%	
		300 Total	502	100%	1.67	456	100%	2.10	958	100%	1.88
Hungary	348	Yes, and rather familiar with it	123	27%		62	13%		185	19%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	271	59%		311	63%		582	61%	
		No, never heard or read about it	65	14%		122	25%		187	20%	
		348 Total	459	100%	1.87	495	100%	2.12	954	100%	2.00
Ireland	372	Yes, and rather familiar with it	132	27%		65	13%		197	20%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	290	60%		266	55%		556	58%	
		No, never heard or read about it	60	12%		151	31%		211	22%	
		372 Total	482	100%	1.85	482	100%	2.18	964	100%	2.01
Italy	380	Yes, and rather familiar with it	210	44%		159	32%		369	38%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	236	49%		267	54%		503	52%	
		No, never heard or read about it	34	7%		66	13%		100	10%	
		380 Total	480	100%	1.63	492	100%	1.81	972	100%	1.72
Latvia	428	Yes, and rather familiar with it	101	23%		64	13%		165	18%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	254	59%		272	56%		526	57%	
		No, never heard or read about it	79	18%		152	31%		231	25%	
		428 Total	434	100%	1.95	488	100%	2.18	922	100%	2.07
Lithuania	440	Yes, and rather familiar with it	111	25%		73	16%		184	20%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	274	62%		241	52%		515	57%	
		No, never heard or read about it	60	13%		151	32%		211	23%	
		440 Total	445	100%	1.89	465	100%	2.17	910	100%	2.03
Luxembourg	442	Yes, and rather familiar with it	126	51%		69	29%		195	40%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	95	38%		119	50%		214	44%	
		No, never heard or read about it	27	11%		48	20%		75	15%	
		442 Total	248	100%	1.60	236	100%	1.91	484	100%	1.75
Malta	470	Yes, and rather familiar with it	114	44%		45	19%		159	32%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	112	43%		128	55%		240	49%	
		No, never heard or read about it	33	13%		61	26%		94	19%	
		470 Total	259	100%	1.69	234	100%	2.07	493	100%	1.87
Netherlands	528	Yes, and rather familiar with it	173	35%		97	20%		270	28%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	285	58%		337	69%		622	64%	
		No, never heard or read about it	31	6%		52	11%		83	9%	
		528 Total	489	100%	1.71	486	100%	1.91	975	100%	1.81
Poland	616	Yes, and rather familiar with it	207	45%		167	34%		374	39%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	224	48%		244	49%		468	49%	
		No, never heard or read about it	34	7%		83	17%		117	12%	
		616 Total	465	100%	1.63	494	100%	1.83	959	100%	1.73
Portugal	620	Yes, and rather familiar with it	108	22%		60	12%		168	17%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	339	70%		375	73%		714	71%	
		No, never heard or read about it	40	8%		78	15%		118	12%	
		620 Total	487	100%	1.86	513	100%	2.04	1000	100%	1.95

Romania	642	Yes, and rather familiar with it	174	36%		125	27%		299	31%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	269	56%		258	55%		527	55%	
		No, never heard or read about it	36	8%		88	19%		124	13%	
	642 Total	479	100%	1.71	471	100%	1.92	950	100%	1.82	
Slovakia	703	Yes, and rather familiar with it	310	67%		186	39%		496	53%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	136	29%		205	43%		341	36%	
		No, never heard or read about it	20	4%		82	17%		102	11%	
	703 Total	466	100%	1.38	473	100%	1.78	939	100%	1.58	
Slovenia	705	Yes, and rather familiar with it	149	31%		65	13%		214	22%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	291	60%		305	63%		596	62%	
		No, never heard or read about it	42	9%		112	23%		154	16%	
	705 Total	482	100%	1.78	482	100%	2.10	964	100%	1.94	
Spain	724	Yes, and rather familiar with it	122	24%		86	17%		208	21%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	320	64%		302	61%		622	63%	
		No, never heard or read about it	59	12%		105	21%		164	16%	
	724 Total	501	100%	1.87	493	100%	2.04	994	100%	1.96	
Sweden	752	Yes, and rather familiar with it	121	26%		60	13%		181	20%	
		Yes, but not at all familiar with it	287	61%		272	60%		559	61%	
		No, never heard or read about it	61	13%		120	27%		181	20%	
	752 Total	469	100%	1.87	452	100%	2.13	921	100%	2.00	
Grand Total			12121	100%	1.77	12286	100%	2.03	24407	100%	1.90

Table 12. Heard and Familiar with Hydrogen Energy (A02_4; All Categories by Gender and Country)

COUNTRY	CODE	A02_4	15-24			25-39			40-54			55-64			65 and above			Grand Total		
			N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}									
Austria	40	Heard and familiar	41	32%		74	33%		72	29%		46	29%		88	41%		321	33%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	68	54%		127	56%		165	65%		103	65%		111	51%		574	59%	
		Never heard and not familiar	18	14%		26	11%		15	6%		9	6%		17	8%		85	9%	
	40 Total	127	100%	1.82	227	100%	1.79	252	100%	1.77	158	100%	1.77	216	100%	1.67	980	100%	1.76	
Belgium	56	Heard and familiar	50	37%		59	24%		48	20%		28	18%		39	17%		224	22%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	62	46%		157	63%		151	61%		112	70%		149	66%		631	62%	
		Never heard and not familiar	22	16%		34	14%		47	19%		20	13%		37	16%		160	16%	
	56 Total	134	100%	1.79	250	100%	1.90	246	100%	2.00	160	100%	1.95	225	100%	1.99	1015	100%	1.94	
Bulgaria	100	Heard and familiar	41	41%		84	36%		90	36%		53	33%		71	31%		339	35%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	47	47%		112	48%		120	48%		92	57%		136	59%		507	52%	
		Never heard and not familiar	13	13%		35	15%		39	16%		16	10%		23	10%		126	13%	
	100 Total	101	100%	1.72	231	100%	1.79	249	100%	1.80	161	100%	1.77	230	100%	1.79	972	100%	1.78	
Croatia	191	Heard and familiar	41	33%		52	24%		48	21%		37	22%		67	30%		245	25%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	61	49%		125	57%		140	61%		110	66%		123	56%		559	58%	
		Never heard and not familiar	23	18%		44	20%		41	18%		20	12%		30	14%		158	16%	
	191 Total	125	100%	1.86	221	100%	1.96	229	100%	1.97	167	100%	1.90	220	100%	1.83	962	100%	1.91	
Cyprus	196	Heard and familiar	27	32%		40	31%		57	43%		20	34%		12	19%		156	33%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	32	38%		40	31%		33	25%		15	26%		8	13%		128	27%	
		Never heard and not familiar	25	30%		51	39%		43	32%		23	40%		42	68%		184	39%	
	196 Total	84	100%	1.98	131	100%	2.08	133	100%	1.89	58	100%	2.05	62	100%	2.48	468	100%	2.06	
Czechia	203	Heard and familiar	22	20%		37	16%		39	16%		17	12%		25	12%		140	15%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	58	54%		135	58%		151	62%		89	64%		133	65%		566	61%	
		Never heard and not familiar	28	26%		60	26%		52	21%		34	24%		47	23%		221	24%	
	203 Total	108	100%	2.06	232	100%	2.10	242	100%	2.05	140	100%	2.12	205	100%	2.11	927	100%	2.09	
Denmark	208	Heard and familiar	62	41%		65	33%		34	15%		29	21%		33	16%		223	24%	

		Heard but not at all familiar	55	36%		90	45%		111	49%		66	47%		86	41%		408	44%	
		Never heard and not familiar	36	24%		43	22%		80	36%		44	32%		90	43%		293	32%	
	208 Total		153	100%	1.83	198	100%	1.89	225	100%	2.20	139	100%	2.11	209	100%	2.27	924	100%	2.08
Estonia	233	Heard and familiar	22	16%		34	15%		30	14%		31	20%		34	16%		151	16%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	78	57%		135	58%		151	69%		96	62%		136	65%		596	62%	
		Never heard and not familiar	38	28%		65	28%		39	18%		27	18%		39	19%		208	22%	
	233 Total		138	100%	2.12	234	100%	2.13	220	100%	2.04	154	100%	1.97	209	100%	2.02	955	100%	2.06
Finland	246	Heard and familiar	34	26%		46	21%		54	25%		33	21%		53	23%		220	23%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	72	55%		126	59%		121	56%		94	61%		148	64%		561	59%	
		Never heard and not familiar	25	19%		43	20%		42	19%		27	18%		30	13%		167	18%	
	246 Total		131	100%	1.93	215	100%	1.99	217	100%	1.94	154	100%	1.96	231	100%	1.90	948	100%	1.94
France	250	Heard and familiar	32	24%		54	27%		56	24%		43	26%		63	29%		248	26%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	80	61%		113	57%		144	61%		96	59%		123	56%		556	59%	
		Never heard and not familiar	20	15%		30	15%		38	16%		25	15%		32	15%		145	15%	
	250 Total		132	100%	1.91	197	100%	1.88	238	100%	1.92	164	100%	1.89	218	100%	1.86	949	100%	1.89
Germany	276	Heard and familiar	45	40%		85	40%		79	33%		69	40%		83	34%		361	37%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	59	52%		106	50%		137	58%		94	55%		151	62%		547	56%	
		Never heard and not familiar	9	8%		23	11%		21	9%		8	5%		10	4%		71	7%	
	276 Total		113	100%	1.68	214	100%	1.71	237	100%	1.76	171	100%	1.64	244	100%	1.70	979	100%	1.70
Greece	300	Heard and familiar	37	35%		74	33%		84	33%		58	38%		87	39%		340	35%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	47	44%		98	43%		107	43%		67	44%		80	36%		399	42%	
		Never heard and not familiar	23	21%		54	24%		60	24%		28	18%		55	25%		220	23%	
	300 Total		107	100%	1.87	226	100%	1.91	251	100%	1.90	153	100%	1.80	222	100%	1.86	959	100%	1.87
Hungary	348	Heard and familiar	33	27%		56	24%		41	17%		27	18%		29	14%		186	19%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	59	48%		134	58%		147	60%		103	68%		141	67%		584	61%	
		Never heard and not familiar	30	25%		40	17%		56	23%		21	14%		40	19%		187	20%	
	348 Total		122	100%	1.98	230	100%	1.93	244	100%	2.06	151	100%	1.96	210	100%	2.05	957	100%	2.00
Ireland	372	Heard and familiar	53	35%		66	26%		45	17%		17	12%		18	11%		199	20%	

		Heard but not at all familiar	77	51%		141	55%		148	57%		81	59%		114	68%		561	58%	
		Never heard and not familiar	22	14%		49	19%		65	25%		40	29%		36	21%		212	22%	
	372 Total		152	100%	1.80	256	100%	1.93	258	100%	2.08	138	100%	2.17	168	100%	2.11	972	100%	2.01
Italy	380	Heard and familiar	55	52%		69	35%		110	42%		54	34%		81	33%		369	38%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	40	38%		102	52%		127	48%		95	59%		139	57%		503	52%	
		Never heard and not familiar	10	10%		27	14%		25	10%		12	7%		26	11%		100	10%	
	380 Total		105	100%	1.57	198	100%	1.79	262	100%	1.68	161	100%	1.74	246	100%	1.78	972	100%	1.72
Latvia	428	Heard and familiar	40	35%		40	17%		30	13%		21	14%		34	16%		165	18%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	43	37%		126	55%		144	64%		92	63%		123	59%		528	57%	
		Never heard and not familiar	32	28%		63	28%		52	23%		34	23%		50	24%		231	25%	
	428 Total		115	100%	1.93	229	100%	2.10	226	100%	2.10	147	100%	2.09	207	100%	2.08	924	100%	2.07
Lithuania	440	Heard and familiar	42	34%		49	23%		40	18%		23	14%		31	16%		185	20%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	56	45%		117	55%		132	60%		98	62%		112	57%		515	57%	
		Never heard and not familiar	26	21%		46	22%		49	22%		38	24%		52	27%		211	23%	
	440 Total		124	100%	1.87	212	100%	1.99	221	100%	2.04	159	100%	2.09	195	100%	2.11	911	100%	2.03
Luxembourg	442	Heard and familiar	24	31%		45	35%		54	41%		39	53%		34	45%		196	40%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	37	48%		59	46%		65	49%		27	36%		27	36%		215	44%	
		Never heard and not familiar	16	21%		24	19%		13	10%		8	11%		15	20%		76	16%	
	442 Total		77	100%	1.90	128	100%	1.84	132	100%	1.69	74	100%	1.58	76	100%	1.75	487	100%	1.75
Malta	470	Heard and familiar	24	35%		44	31%		33	29%		25	38%		33	31%		159	32%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	26	38%		69	49%		53	47%		31	47%		61	58%		240	49%	
		Never heard and not familiar	19	28%		27	19%		27	24%		10	15%		12	11%		95	19%	
	470 Total		69	100%	1.93	140	100%	1.88	113	100%	1.95	66	100%	1.77	106	100%	1.80	494	100%	1.87
Netherlands	528	Heard and familiar	44	31%		73	33%		66	28%		42	28%		46	21%		271	28%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	83	58%		128	58%		145	61%		100	66%		168	75%		624	64%	
		Never heard and not familiar	17	12%		21	9%		25	11%		10	7%		10	4%		83	8%	
	528 Total		144	100%	1.81	222	100%	1.77	236	100%	1.83	152	100%	1.79	224	100%	1.84	978	100%	1.81
Poland	616	Heard and familiar	44	35%		99	37%		86	39%		68	44%		78	41%		375	39%	

		Heard but not at all familiar	54	43%		137	51%		108	49%		74	48%		95	49%		468	49%	
		Never heard and not familiar	27	22%		32	12%		26	12%		13	8%		19	10%		117	12%	
		616 Total	125	100%	1.86	268	100%	1.75	220	100%	1.73	155	100%	1.65	192	100%	1.69	960	100%	1.73
Portugal	620	Heard and familiar	19	16%		46	22%		44	16%		30	19%		29	12%		168	17%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	81	67%		139	66%		191	71%		116	72%		188	78%		715	71%	
		Never heard and not familiar	21	17%		25	12%		33	12%		16	10%		23	10%		118	12%	
		620 Total	121	100%	2.02	210	100%	1.90	268	100%	1.96	162	100%	1.91	240	100%	1.98	1001	100%	1.95
Romania	642	Heard and familiar	56	47%		78	34%		74	29%		37	25%		54	27%		299	31%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	50	42%		125	55%		142	56%		92	61%		118	60%		527	55%	
		Never heard and not familiar	14	12%		25	11%		37	15%		22	15%		26	13%		124	13%	
		642 Total	120	100%	1.65	228	100%	1.77	253	100%	1.85	151	100%	1.90	198	100%	1.86	950	100%	1.82
Slovakia	703	Heard and familiar	71	58%		159	61%		112	46%		71	48%		84	51%		497	53%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	41	33%		76	29%		100	41%		60	40%		64	39%		341	36%	
		Never heard and not familiar	11	9%		25	10%		33	13%		18	12%		16	10%		103	11%	
		703 Total	123	100%	1.51	260	100%	1.48	245	100%	1.68	149	100%	1.64	164	100%	1.59	941	100%	1.58
Slovenia	705	Heard and familiar	28	25%		51	23%		59	24%		30	18%		46	22%		214	22%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	59	54%		134	59%		161	64%		106	64%		136	64%		596	62%	
		Never heard and not familiar	23	21%		41	18%		31	12%		30	18%		29	14%		154	16%	
		705 Total	110	100%	1.95	226	100%	1.96	251	100%	1.89	166	100%	2.00	211	100%	1.92	964	100%	1.94
Spain	724	Heard and familiar	29	27%		60	27%		61	21%		27	17%		31	14%		208	21%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	55	50%		136	60%		177	62%		109	68%		147	69%		624	63%	
		Never heard and not familiar	25	23%		30	13%		49	17%		24	15%		36	17%		164	16%	
		724 Total	109	100%	1.96	226	100%	1.87	287	100%	1.96	160	100%	1.98	214	100%	2.02	996	100%	1.96
Sweden	752	Heard and familiar	30	23%		49	22%		40	18%		27	20%		36	17%		182	20%	
		Heard but not at all familiar	67	51%		123	55%		134	61%		88	64%		148	68%		560	61%	
		Never heard and not familiar	34	26%		50	23%		44	20%		22	16%		33	15%		183	20%	
		752 Total	131	100%	2.03	222	100%	2.00	218	100%	2.02	137	100%	1.96	217	100%	1.99	925	100%	2.00
	Grand Total	3200		1.86	5831		1.89	6173		1.92	3907		1.90	5359		1.92	24470		1.90	

B07. To what extent do you agree or disagree with each of the following statements regarding Hydrogen energy and technologies?

B07.2. Hydrogen is a good solution for reducing the energy dependence of [Country]

Table 13. Gender of respondents for 'Hydrogen is a good solution for reducing the energy dependence' (B07_2)

D03 Gender		N	%	\bar{x}
Male	1	10908	53%	
Female	2	9708	47%	
Grand Total		20616	100%	1.47

Table 14. Age of respondents for 'Hydrogen is a good solution for reducing the energy dependence' (B07_2)

D02A Age		N	%	\bar{x}
15-24	1	2849	14%	
25-39	2	5017	24%	
40-54	3	5205	25%	
55-64	4	3217	16%	
65 and above	5	4379	21%	
Grand Total		20667	100%	3.06

Table 15. Country of respondents for 'Hydrogen is a good solution for reducing the energy dependence' (B07_2)

Country	Code	N	%	\bar{x}
Austria	40	881	4%	1.85
Belgium	56	819	4%	1.95
Bulgaria	100	852	4%	1.94
Croatia	191	838	4%	1.94
Cyprus	196	352	2%	1.79
Czechia	203	793	4%	2.13
Denmark	208	704	3%	1.93
Estonia	233	769	4%	2.12
Finland	246	758	4%	1.99
France	250	795	4%	1.87
Germany	276	886	4%	1.82
Greece	300	832	4%	1.92
Hungary	348	794	4%	2.05
Ireland	372	790	4%	1.91
Italy	380	863	4%	1.81
Latvia	428	738	4%	2.18

Lithuania	440	751	4%	2.03
Luxembourg	442	430	2%	1.90
Malta	470	431	2%	1.83
Netherlands	528	826	4%	1.88
Poland	616	848	4%	1.85
Portugal	620	908	4%	1.74
Romania	642	865	4%	1.88
Slovakia	703	781	4%	2.11
Slovenia	705	778	4%	2.06
Spain	724	896	4%	1.93
Sweden	752	689	3%	2.13
Grand Total		20667	100%	1.95

Table 16. Levels of Agreement about Energy Dependence (B07_2; All Categories)

B07_2		N	%	\bar{x}
Totally agree	1	5580	27%	
Tend to agree	2	11386	55%	
Tend to disagree	3	2822	14%	
Totally disagree	4	828	4%	
Grand Total		20616	100%	1.95

Table 17. Levels of Agreement about Energy Dependence (B07_2; All Categories, Gender)

Energy Dependence B07_2	D03	Male			Female			Grand Total		
		N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}
Totally agree	1	3239	30%		2341	24%		5580	27%	
Tend to agree	2	5664	52%		5722	59%		11386	55%	
Tend to disagree	3	1529	14%		1293	13%		2822	14%	
Totally disagree	4	476	4%		352	4%		828	4%	
Grand Total		10908	100%	1.93	9708	100%	1.96	20616	100%	1.94

Table 18. Levels of Agreement about Energy Dependence (B07_2; All Categories, Gender and Country)

COUNTRY	D03	Male			Female			Grand Total			
		B07_2	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}
Austria	40	Totally agree	144	51%		141	49%		285	100%	
		Tend to agree	235	50%		236	50%		471	100%	
		Tend to disagree	51	53%		45	47%		96	100%	
		Totally disagree	17	63%		10	37%		27	100%	
	40 Total		447	51%	1.87	432	49%	1.82	879	100%	1.85
Belgium	56	Totally agree	135	63%		79	37%		214	100%	
		Tend to agree	223	48%		245	52%		468	100%	
		Tend to disagree	50	50%		50	50%		100	100%	
		Totally disagree	23	64%		13	36%		36	100%	
	56 Total		431	53%	1.91	387	47%	1.99	818	100%	1.95

Bulgaria	100	Totally agree	126	53%		110	47%		236	100%	
		Tend to agree	238	51%		226	49%		464	100%	
		Tend to disagree	46	41%		66	59%		112	100%	
		Totally disagree	21	55%		17	45%		38	100%	
	100 Total	431	51%	1.91	419	49%	1.98	850	100%	1.94	
Croatia	191	Totally agree	133	53%		117	47%		250	100%	
		Tend to agree	222	52%		208	48%		430	100%	
		Tend to disagree	73	65%		40	35%		113	100%	
		Totally disagree	21	49%		22	51%		43	100%	
	191 Total	449	54%	1.96	387	46%	1.91	836	100%	1.94	
Cyprus	196	Totally agree	76	58%		56	42%		132	100%	
		Tend to agree	75	44%		95	56%		170	100%	
		Tend to disagree	24	59%		17	41%		41	100%	
		Totally disagree	6	67%		3	33%		9	100%	
	196 Total	181	51%	1.78	171	49%	1.81	352	100%	1.79	
Czechia	203	Totally agree	86	64%		49	36%		135	100%	
		Tend to agree	244	52%		223	48%		467	100%	
		Tend to disagree	79	55%		64	45%		143	100%	
		Totally disagree	21	48%		23	52%		44	100%	
	203 Total	430	54%	2.08	359	46%	2.17	789	100%	2.12	
Denmark	208	Totally agree	103	62%		64	38%		167	100%	
		Tend to agree	227	53%		202	47%		429	100%	
		Tend to disagree	42	49%		43	51%		85	100%	
		Totally disagree	11	65%		6	35%		17	100%	
	208 Total	383	55%	1.90	315	45%	1.97	698	100%	1.93	
Estonia	233	Totally agree	84	57%		64	43%		148	100%	
		Tend to agree	208	49%		214	51%		422	100%	
		Tend to disagree	90	57%		67	43%		157	100%	
		Totally disagree	26	62%		16	38%		42	100%	
	233 Total	408	53%	2.14	361	47%	2.10	769	100%	2.12	
Finland	246	Totally agree	107	60%		71	40%		178	100%	
		Tend to agree	216	50%		219	50%		435	100%	
		Tend to disagree	75	68%		36	32%		111	100%	
		Totally disagree	21	68%		10	32%		31	100%	4.00
	246 Total	419	55%	2.02	336	45%	1.96	755	100%	1.99	
France	250	Totally agree	138	56%		107	44%		245	100%	
		Tend to agree	223	52%		210	48%		433	100%	
		Tend to disagree	46	54%		39	46%		85	100%	
		Totally disagree	18	62%		11	38%		29	100%	
	250 Total	425	54%	1.87	367	46%	1.87	792	100%	1.87	
Germany	276	Totally agree	178	56%		140	44%		318	100%	
		Tend to agree	213	49%		225	51%		438	100%	
		Tend to disagree	50	50%		50	50%		100	100%	
		Totally disagree	18	62%		11	38%		29	100%	
	276 Total	459	52%	1.80	426	48%	1.84	885	100%	1.82	
Greece	300	Totally agree	144	66%		74	34%		218	100%	

		Tend to agree	254	51%		244	49%		498	100%
		Tend to disagree	41	52%		38	48%		79	100%
		Totally disagree	23	64%		13	36%		36	100%
		300 Total	462	56%	1.88	369	44%	1.97	831	100%
Hungary	348	Totally agree	101	59%		69	41%		170	100%
		Tend to agree	209	47%		240	53%		449	100%
		Tend to disagree	84	64%		47	36%		131	100%
		Totally disagree	20	49%		21	51%		41	100%
		348 Total	414	52%	2.06	377	48%	2.05	791	100%
Ireland	372	Totally agree	133	65%		71	35%		204	100%
		Tend to agree	238	50%		235	50%		473	100%
		Tend to disagree	49	59%		34	41%		83	100%
		Totally disagree	9	41%		13	59%		22	100%
		372 Total	429	55%	1.85	353	45%	1.97	782	100%
Italy	380	Totally agree	159	56%		125	44%		284	100%
		Tend to agree	234	49%		247	51%		481	100%
		Tend to disagree	38	52%		35	48%		73	100%
		Totally disagree	11	44%		14	56%		25	100%
		380 Total	442	51%	1.78	421	49%	1.85	863	100%
Latvia	428	Totally agree	80	63%		48	38%		128	100%
		Tend to agree	183	46%		217	54%		400	100%
		Tend to disagree	81	52%		76	48%		157	100%
		Totally disagree	30	59%		21	41%		51	100%
		428 Total	374	51%	2.16	362	49%	2.19	736	100%
Lithuania	440	Totally agree	96	59%		67	41%		163	100%
		Tend to agree	214	50%		213	50%		427	100%
		Tend to disagree	71	53%		62	47%		133	100%
		Totally disagree	11	41%		16	59%		27	100%
		440 Total	392	52%	1.99	358	48%	2.08	750	100%
Luxembourg	442	Totally agree	72	58%		52	42%		124	100%
		Tend to agree	125	52%		114	48%		239	100%
		Tend to disagree	25	52%		23	48%		48	100%
		Totally disagree	9	53%		8	47%		17	100%
		442 Total	231	54%	1.87	197	46%	1.93	428	100%
Malta	470	Totally agree	87	58%		62	42%		149	100%
		Tend to agree	108	50%		109	50%		217	100%
		Tend to disagree	35	66%		18	34%		53	100%
		Totally disagree	8	73%		3	27%		11	100%
		470 Total	238	55%	1.85	192	45%	1.80	430	100%
Netherlands	528	Totally agree	144	62%		88	38%		232	100%
		Tend to agree	236	49%		242	51%		478	100%
		Tend to disagree	47	49%		48	51%		95	100%
		Totally disagree	13	65%		7	35%		20	100%
		528 Total	440	53%	1.84	385	47%	1.93	825	100%
Poland	616	Totally agree	145	57%		109	43%		254	100%
		Tend to agree	234	47%		259	53%		493	100%

	Tend to disagree	35	48%		38	52%		73	100%	
	Totally disagree	15	56%		12	44%		27	100%	
	616 Total	429	51%	1.81	418	49%	1.89	847	100%	1.85
Portugal	620 Totally agree	181	55%		146	45%		327	100%	
	Tend to agree	234	47%		268	53%		502	100%	
	Tend to disagree	35	56%		27	44%		62	100%	
	Totally disagree	9	56%		7	44%		16	100%	
	620 Total	459	51%	1.72	448	49%	1.77	907	100%	1.74
Romania	642 Totally agree	153	55%		125	45%		278	100%	
	Tend to agree	213	47%		236	53%		449	100%	
	Tend to disagree	59	57%		45	43%		104	100%	
	Totally disagree	17	50%		17	50%		34	100%	
	642 Total	442	51%	1.86	423	49%	1.89	865	100%	1.88
Slovakia	703 Totally agree	92	57%		69	43%		161	100%	
	Tend to agree	214	51%		209	49%		423	100%	
	Tend to disagree	73	49%		75	51%		148	100%	
	Totally disagree	33	67%		16	33%		49	100%	
	703 Total	412	53%	2.11	369	47%	2.10	781	100%	2.11
Slovenia	705 Totally agree	111	59%		78	41%		189	100%	
	Tend to agree	206	53%		185	47%		391	100%	
	Tend to disagree	84	53%		75	47%		159	100%	
	Totally disagree	25	64%		14	36%		39	100%	
	705 Total	426	55%	2.05	352	45%	2.07	778	100%	2.06
Spain	724 Totally agree	152	60%		102	40%		254	100%	
	Tend to agree	231	49%		244	51%		475	100%	
	Tend to disagree	67	47%		76	53%		143	100%	
	Totally disagree	12	55%		10	45%		22	100%	
	724 Total	462	52%	1.87	432	48%	1.99	894	100%	1.93
Sweden	752 Totally agree	79	58%		58	42%		137	100%	
	Tend to agree	207	57%		157	43%		364	100%	
	Tend to disagree	79	57%		59	43%		138	100%	
	Totally disagree	28	61%		18	39%		46	100%	
	752 Total	393	57%	2.14	292	43%	2.13	685	100%	2.14
Grand Total		10908	53%	1.93	9708	47%	1.96	20616	100%	1.95

B07.3. Hydrogen is a sustainable energy source

Table 19. Gender of respondents for 'Hydrogen is a sustainable energy source' (B07_2)

D03 Gender		N	%	\bar{x}
Male	1	10682	54%	
Female	2	9151	46%	
Grand Total		19833	100%	1.46

Table 20. Responses to 'Hydrogen is a sustainable energy source' (B07_2)

B07_3		N	%	\bar{x}
Totally agree	1	5559	28%	
Tend to agree	2	11117	56%	
Tend to disagree	3	2547	13%	
Totally disagree	4	660	3%	
Grand Total		19883	100%	1.91

Table 21. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Sustainability (B07_3; All Categories, Gender)

D03 Sustainable B07_3	Male			Female			Grand Total		
	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}
Totally agree	1	3328	31%	2223	24%		5551	28%	
Tend to agree	2	5604	52%	5484	60%		11088	56%	
Tend to disagree	3	1372	13%	1168	13%		2540	13%	
Totally disagree	4	378	4%	276	3%		654	3%	
Grand Total		10682	100%	9151	100%	1.95	19833	100%	1.91

Table 22. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Sustainability (B07_3; All Categories, Gender and Country)

COUNTRY	D03 Sustainable B07_3	Male			Female			Grand Total		
		N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}
Austria	40 Totally agree	135	31%		110	28%		245	29%	
	Tend to agree	231	53%		239	60%		470	56%	
	Tend to disagree	55	13%		38	10%		93	11%	
	Totally disagree	16	4%		13	3%		29	3%	
	40 Total	437	100%	1.89	400	100%	1.89	837	100%	1.89
Belgium	56 Totally agree	126	30%		83	24%		209	27%	
	Tend to agree	222	53%		205	58%		427	55%	
	Tend to disagree	50	12%		52	15%		102	13%	
	Totally disagree	21	5%		11	3%		32	4%	
	56 Total	419	100%	1.92	351	100%	1.97	770	100%	1.94
Bulgaria	100 Totally agree	117	28%		84	23%		201	26%	
	Tend to agree	228	55%		223	61%		451	58%	
	Tend to disagree	57	14%		48	13%		105	13%	
	Totally disagree	16	4%		10	3%		26	3%	
	100 Total	418	100%	1.93	365	100%	1.96	783	100%	1.94
Croatia	191 Totally agree	139	32%		101	30%		240	31%	
	Tend to agree	233	53%		198	58%		431	55%	
	Tend to disagree	56	13%		35	10%		91	12%	
	Totally disagree	10	2%		8	2%		18	2%	
	191 Total	438	100%	1.86	342	100%	1.85	780	100%	1.86

Cyprus	196	Totally agree	75	41%	58	35%	133	38%		
		Tend to agree	86	47%	89	54%	175	50%		
		Tend to disagree	17	9%	13	8%	30	9%		
		Totally disagree	5	3%	4	2%	9	3%		
	196 Total		183	100%	1.74	164	100%	1.77	347	100%
Czechia	203	Totally agree	102	24%	56	16%	158	20%		
		Tend to agree	246	57%	235	68%	481	62%		
		Tend to disagree	68	16%	44	13%	112	14%		
		Totally disagree	17	4%	12	3%	29	4%		
	203 Total		433	100%	2.00	347	100%	2.03	780	100%
Denmark	208	Totally agree	103	27%	67	22%	170	25%		
		Tend to agree	205	54%	179	60%	384	57%		
		Tend to disagree	53	14%	49	16%	102	15%		
		Totally disagree	16	4%	4	1%	20	3%		
	208 Total		377	100%	1.95	299	100%	1.97	676	100%
Estonia	233	Totally agree	87	22%	57	16%	144	19%		
		Tend to agree	208	52%	218	61%	426	56%		
		Tend to disagree	81	20%	66	19%	147	19%		
		Totally disagree	27	7%	14	4%	41	5%		
	233 Total		403	100%	2.12	355	100%	2.10	758	100%
Finland	246	Totally agree	125	31%	46	16%	171	25%		
		Tend to agree	213	52%	187	66%	400	58%		
		Tend to disagree	60	15%	36	13%	96	14%		
		Totally disagree	11	3%	15	5%	26	4%		
	246 Total		409	100%	1.89	284	100%	2.07	693	100%
France	250	Totally agree	141	34%	80	24%	221	30%		
		Tend to agree	210	51%	203	62%	413	56%		
		Tend to disagree	50	12%	31	9%	81	11%		
		Totally disagree	11	3%	16	5%	27	4%		
	250 Total		412	100%	1.83	330	100%	1.95	742	100%
Germany	276	Totally agree	169	37%	136	33%	305	35%		
		Tend to agree	220	48%	226	54%	446	51%		
		Tend to disagree	45	10%	49	12%	94	11%		
		Totally disagree	20	4%	6	1%	26	3%		
	276 Total		454	100%	1.81	417	100%	1.82	871	100%
Greece	300	Totally agree	150	33%	68	20%	218	27%		
		Tend to agree	237	53%	236	68%	473	60%		
		Tend to disagree	43	10%	37	11%	80	10%		
		Totally disagree	18	4%	5	1%	23	3%		
	300 Total		448	100%	1.84	346	100%	1.94	794	100%
Hungary	348	Totally agree	124	30%	72	19%	196	25%		
		Tend to agree	221	53%	252	66%	473	59%		
		Tend to disagree	56	13%	44	12%	100	13%		
		Totally disagree	17	4%	13	3%	30	4%		
	348 Total		418	100%	1.92	381	100%	1.99	799	100%
Ireland	372	Totally agree	129	31%	81	24%	210	28%		
		Tend to agree	237	57%	222	65%	459	61%		
		Tend to disagree	40	10%	31	9%	71	9%		
		Totally disagree	10	2%	6	2%	16	2%		

	372 Total	416	100%	1.83	340	100%	1.89	756	100%	1.86
Italy	380 Totally agree	173	40%		131	32%		304	36%	
	Tend to agree	226	52%		228	56%		454	54%	
	Tend to disagree	31	7%		42	10%		73	9%	
	Totally disagree	6	1%		8	2%		14	2%	
	380 Total	436	100%	1.70	409	100%	1.82	845	100%	1.76
Latvia	428 Totally agree	98	26%		51	15%		149	21%	
	Tend to agree	193	52%		218	65%		411	58%	
	Tend to disagree	62	17%		56	17%		118	17%	
	Totally disagree	19	5%		12	4%		31	4%	
	428 Total	372	100%	2.01	337	100%	2.09	709	100%	2.04
Lithuania	440 Totally agree	86	23%		54	17%		140	20%	
	Tend to agree	211	57%		211	65%		422	61%	
	Tend to disagree	64	17%		52	16%		116	17%	
	Totally disagree	8	2%		10	3%		18	3%	
	440 Total	369	100%	1.98	327	100%	2.06	696	100%	2.02
Luxembourg	442 Totally agree	86	38%		47	26%		133	33%	
	Tend to agree	104	46%		102	56%		206	50%	
	Tend to disagree	28	12%		26	14%		54	13%	
	Totally disagree	8	4%		8	4%		16	4%	
	442 Total	226	100%	1.81	183	100%	1.97	409	100%	1.89
Malta	470 Totally agree	110	46%		58	32%		168	40%	
	Tend to agree	105	44%		113	61%		218	52%	
	Tend to disagree	20	8%		9	5%		29	7%	
	Totally disagree	2	1%		4	2%		6	1%	
	470 Total	237	100%	1.64	184	100%	1.78	421	100%	1.70
Netherlands	528 Totally agree	141	32%		93	25%		234	29%	
	Tend to agree	227	52%		224	61%		451	56%	
	Tend to disagree	48	11%		41	11%		89	11%	
	Totally disagree	18	4%		10	3%		28	3%	
	528 Total	434	100%	1.87	368	100%	1.91	802	100%	1.89
Poland	616 Totally agree	122	30%		107	27%		229	28%	
	Tend to agree	239	58%		245	61%		484	60%	
	Tend to disagree	38	9%		33	8%		71	9%	
	Totally disagree	12	3%		14	4%		26	3%	
	616 Total	411	100%	1.85	399	100%	1.88	810	100%	1.87
Portugal	620 Totally agree	167	38%		138	32%		305	35%	
	Tend to agree	242	55%		258	59%		500	57%	
	Tend to disagree	28	6%		33	8%		61	7%	
	Totally disagree	5	1%		5	1%		10	1%	
	620 Total	442	100%	1.71	434	100%	1.78	876	100%	1.74
Romania	642 Totally agree	160	36%		131	31%		291	34%	
	Tend to agree	224	51%		226	54%		450	53%	
	Tend to disagree	46	10%		51	12%		97	11%	
	Totally disagree	9	2%		10	2%		19	2%	
	642 Total	439	100%	1.78	418	100%	1.86	857	100%	1.82
Slovakia	703 Totally agree	103	26%		73	21%		176	23%	
	Tend to agree	214	53%		209	59%		423	56%	
	Tend to disagree	69	17%		60	17%		129	17%	

	Totally disagree	16	4%	13	4%	29	4%
	703 Total	402	100%	2.00	355	100%	2.04
Slovenia	705 Totally agree	123	30%	79	24%	202	27%
	Tend to agree	187	45%	164	49%	351	47%
	Tend to disagree	84	20%	78	23%	162	22%
	Totally disagree	21	5%	12	4%	33	4%
	705 Total	415	100%	2.01	333	100%	2.07
Spain	724 Totally agree	148	32%	108	26%	256	29%
	Tend to agree	235	51%	242	57%	477	54%
	Tend to disagree	54	12%	59	14%	113	13%
	Totally disagree	20	4%	12	3%	32	4%
	724 Total	457	100%	1.88	421	100%	1.94
Sweden	752 Totally agree	89	24%	54	21%	143	22%
	Tend to agree	200	53%	132	50%	332	52%
	Tend to disagree	69	18%	55	21%	124	19%
	Totally disagree	19	5%	21	8%	40	6%
	752 Total	377	100%	2.05	262	100%	2.16
Grand Total		10682		1.89	9151		1.95
						19833	1.91

B07.6. The use of Hydrogen is as safe as the use of any other energy source

Table 23. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Safety (B07_6; Gender)

D03		N	%	\bar{x}
Male	1	10346	55%	
Female	2	8370	45%	
Grand Total		18716	100%	1.45

Table 24. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Safety (B07_6; All Categories)

B07_6		N	%	\bar{x}
Totally agree	1	4137	22%	
Tend to agree	2	9685	52%	
Tend to disagree	3	3954	21%	
Totally disagree	4	985	5%	
Grand Total		18761	100%	2.09

Table 25. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Safety (B07_6; All Categories, Gender)

Safety B07_6	D03	Male			Female			Grand Total		
		N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}
Totally agree	1	2479	24%		1649	20%		4128	22%	
Tend to agree	2	5063	49%		4602	55%		9665	52%	
Tend to disagree	3	2208	21%		1733	21%		3941	21%	
Totally disagree	4	596	6%		386	5%		982	5%	
Grand Total		10346	100%	2.09	8370	100%	2.10	18716	100%	2.09

Table 26. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Safety (B07_6; All Categories, Gender and Country)

COUNTRY	D03	Male			Female			Grand Total			
		B07_6	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}
Austria	40	Totally agree	121	28%		88	23%		209	26%	
		Tend to agree	193	45%		204	54%		397	49%	
		Tend to disagree	90	21%		77	20%		167	21%	
		Totally disagree	22	5%		11	3%		33	4%	
		40 Total	426	100%	2.03	380	100%	2.03	806	100%	2.03
Belgium	56	Totally agree	105	26%		57	19%		162	23%	
		Tend to agree	193	48%		164	54%		357	50%	
		Tend to disagree	81	20%		70	23%		151	21%	
		Totally disagree	27	7%		15	5%		42	6%	
		56 Total	406	100%	2.07	306	100%	2.14	712	100%	2.10
Bulgaria	100	Totally agree	80	20%		62	17%		142	18%	
		Tend to agree	187	46%		171	47%		358	46%	
		Tend to disagree	116	28%		108	30%		224	29%	
		Totally disagree	26	6%		22	6%		48	6%	
		100 Total	409	100%	2.22	363	100%	2.25	772	100%	2.23
Croatia	191	Totally agree	130	31%		77	24%		207	28%	
		Tend to agree	181	43%		172	54%		353	48%	

	Tend to disagree	85	20%		51	16%		136	18%
	Totally disagree	24	6%		16	5%		40	5%
	191 Total	420	100%	2.01	316	100%	2.02	736	100%
Cyprus	Totally agree	50	31%		39	29%		89	30%
	Tend to agree	69	43%		57	43%		126	43%
	Tend to disagree	27	17%		33	25%		60	20%
	Totally disagree	14	9%		5	4%		19	6%
	196 Total	160	100%	2.03	134	100%	2.03	294	100%
Czechia	Totally agree	69	16%		34	11%		103	14%
	Tend to agree	207	49%		164	53%		371	51%
	Tend to disagree	116	28%		79	25%		195	27%
	Totally disagree	27	6%		33	11%		60	8%
	203 Total	419	100%	2.24	310	100%	2.36	729	100%
Denmark	Totally agree	78	22%		43	17%		121	20%
	Tend to agree	187	54%		152	60%		339	56%
	Tend to disagree	67	19%		47	19%		114	19%
	Totally disagree	16	5%		12	5%		28	5%
	208 Total	348	100%	2.06	254	100%	2.11	602	100%
Estonia	Totally agree	69	18%		36	12%		105	15%
	Tend to agree	179	46%		151	52%		330	48%
	Tend to disagree	107	28%		91	31%		198	29%
	Totally disagree	34	9%		15	5%		49	7%
	233 Total	389	100%	2.27	293	100%	2.29	682	100%
Finland	Totally agree	87	21%		32	12%		119	17%
	Tend to agree	209	51%		158	57%		367	54%
	Tend to disagree	96	24%		71	26%		167	24%
	Totally disagree	16	4%		15	5%		31	5%
	246 Total	408	100%	2.10	276	100%	2.25	684	100%
France	Totally agree	97	24%		72	23%		169	24%
	Tend to agree	198	49%		168	54%		366	51%
	Tend to disagree	84	21%		53	17%		137	19%
	Totally disagree	24	6%		18	6%		42	6%
	250 Total	403	100%	2.09	311	100%	2.05	714	100%
Germany	Totally agree	130	30%		94	24%		224	27%
	Tend to agree	216	49%		214	55%		430	52%
	Tend to disagree	73	17%		71	18%		144	17%
	Totally disagree	21	5%		10	3%		31	4%
	276 Total	440	100%	1.97	389	100%	1.99	829	100%
Greece	Totally agree	121	28%		56	19%		177	24%
	Tend to agree	219	51%		170	58%		389	54%
	Tend to disagree	67	16%		61	21%		128	18%
	Totally disagree	23	5%		7	2%		30	4%
	300 Total	430	100%	1.98	294	100%	2.06	724	100%
Hungary	Totally agree	85	21%		55	15%		140	18%
	Tend to agree	202	49%		216	60%		418	54%
	Tend to disagree	99	24%		69	19%		168	22%
	Totally disagree	23	6%		21	6%		44	6%
	348 Total	409	100%	2.15	361	100%	2.16	770	100%
Ireland	Totally agree	93	23%		68	22%		161	22%

	Tend to agree	233	57%		208	66%		441	61%	
	Tend to disagree	68	17%		30	10%		98	14%	
	Totally disagree	15	4%		7	2%		22	3%	
	372 Total	409	100%	2.01	313	100%	1.92	722	100%	1.97
Italy	380 Totally agree	111	26%		90	23%		201	25%	
	Tend to agree	238	57%		219	57%		457	57%	
	Tend to disagree	54	13%		61	16%		115	14%	
	Totally disagree	18	4%		16	4%		34	4%	
	380 Total	421	100%	1.95	386	100%	2.01	807	100%	1.98
Latvia	428 Totally agree	53	15%		35	11%		88	13%	
	Tend to agree	162	45%		156	51%		318	47%	
	Tend to disagree	112	31%		97	31%		209	31%	
	Totally disagree	36	10%		20	6%		56	8%	
	428 Total	363	100%	2.36	308	100%	2.33	671	100%	2.35
Lithuania	440 Totally agree	56	15%		41	13%		97	14%	
	Tend to agree	171	47%		193	62%		364	54%	
	Tend to disagree	114	31%		61	20%		175	26%	
	Totally disagree	26	7%		15	5%		41	6%	
	440 Total	367	100%	2.30	310	100%	2.16	677	100%	2.24
Luxembourg	442 Totally agree	54	24%		33	18%		87	22%	
	Tend to agree	100	45%		88	49%		188	47%	
	Tend to disagree	57	25%		47	26%		104	26%	
	Totally disagree	13	6%		11	6%		24	6%	
	442 Total	224	100%	2.13	179	100%	2.20	403	100%	2.16
Malta	470 Totally agree	82	36%		48	28%		130	32%	
	Tend to agree	96	42%		94	55%		190	47%	
	Tend to disagree	36	16%		22	13%		58	14%	
	Totally disagree	15	7%		8	5%		23	6%	
	470 Total	229	100%	1.93	172	100%	1.94	401	100%	1.94
Netherlands	528 Totally agree	98	24%		57	19%		155	22%	
	Tend to agree	202	49%		182	61%		384	54%	
	Tend to disagree	87	21%		47	16%		134	19%	
	Totally disagree	23	6%		11	4%		34	5%	
	528 Total	410	100%	2.09	297	100%	2.04	707	100%	2.07
Poland	616 Totally agree	98	24%		85	23%		183	24%	
	Tend to agree	216	54%		224	61%		440	57%	
	Tend to disagree	73	18%		46	13%		119	15%	
	Totally disagree	15	4%		11	3%		26	3%	
	616 Total	402	100%	2.01	366	100%	1.95	768	100%	1.98
Portugal	620 Totally agree	129	31%		97	25%		226	28%	
	Tend to agree	230	55%		233	61%		463	58%	
	Tend to disagree	52	12%		42	11%		94	12%	
	Totally disagree	6	1%		13	3%		19	2%	
	620 Total	417	100%	1.84	385	100%	1.92	802	100%	1.88
Romania	642 Totally agree	131	30%		108	27%		239	29%	
	Tend to agree	214	50%		211	53%		425	51%	
	Tend to disagree	65	15%		67	17%		132	16%	
	Totally disagree	21	5%		10	3%		31	4%	
	642 Total	431	100%	1.94	396	100%	1.95	827	100%	1.95

Slovakia	703	Totally agree	76	19%		55	16%		131	18%	
		Tend to agree	181	45%		168	50%		349	47%	
		Tend to disagree	107	27%		96	28%		203	27%	
		Totally disagree	38	9%		19	6%		57	8%	
	703 Total		402	100%	2.27	338	100%	2.23	740	100%	2.25
Slovenia	705	Totally agree	97	24%		55	18%		152	21%	
		Tend to agree	164	40%		147	47%		311	43%	
		Tend to disagree	117	29%		91	29%		208	29%	
		Totally disagree	30	7%		21	7%		51	7%	
	705 Total		408	100%	2.20	314	100%	2.25	722	100%	2.22
Spain	724	Totally agree	119	27%		92	23%		211	25%	
		Tend to agree	243	55%		219	55%		462	55%	
		Tend to disagree	62	14%		77	19%		139	17%	
		Totally disagree	14	3%		9	2%		23	3%	
	724 Total		438	100%	1.93	397	100%	2.01	835	100%	1.97
Sweden	752	Totally agree	60	17%		40	18%		100	17%	
		Tend to agree	173	48%		99	45%		272	47%	
		Tend to disagree	96	27%		68	31%		164	28%	
		Totally disagree	29	8%		15	7%		44	8%	
	752 Total		358	100%	2.26	222	100%	2.26	580	100%	2.26
Grand Total			10346	55%	2.09	8370	45%	2.10	18,716	100%	2.09

B07.5. Hydrogen is as polluting as Diesel or gasoline

Table 27. Respondents by gender for levels of agreement about Hydrogen Polluting (B07_5; Gender)

D03 Gender		N	%	\bar{x}
Male	1	10592	55%	
Female	2	8781	45%	
Grand Total		19373	100%	1.45

Table 28. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Polluting (B07_5; All Categories)

B07_5		N	%	\bar{x}
Totally agree	1	1516	8%	
Tend to agree	2	3515	18%	
Tend to disagree	3	7305	38%	
Totally disagree	4	7087	36%	
Grand Total		19423	100%	3.03

Table 29. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Polluting (B07_5; All Categories, Gender)

Polluting B07_5	D03	Male			Female			Grand Total		
		N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}
Totally agree	1	831	8%		677	8%		1508	8%	
Tend to agree	2	1746	16%		1762	20%		3508	18%	
Tend to disagree	3	3455	33%		3831	44%		7286	38%	
Totally disagree	4	4560	43%		2511	29%		7071	36%	
Grand Total		10592	100%	3.11	8781	100%	2.93	19373	100%	3.03

Table 30. Levels of Agreement about Hydrogen Polluting (B07_5; All Categories, Gender and Country)

COUNTRY	B07_5	D03 Male			D03 Female			Grand Total		
		N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}	N	%	\bar{x}
Austria	40 Totally agree	24	6%		29	7%		53	6%	
	Tend to agree	60	14%		67	17%		127	15%	
	Tend to disagree	155	36%		173	44%		328	40%	
	Totally disagree	193	45%		125	32%		318	38%	
	40 Total	432	100%	3.20	394	100%	3.00	826	100%	3.10
Belgium	56 Totally agree	49	12%		33	9%		82	11%	
	Tend to agree	63	15%		68	19%		131	17%	
	Tend to disagree	123	30%		133	38%		256	34%	
	Totally disagree	173	42%		116	33%		289	38%	
	56 Total	408	100%	3.03	350	100%	2.95	758	100%	2.99
Bulgaria	100 Totally agree	36	9%		23	6%		59	8%	
	Tend to agree	62	15%		76	21%		138	18%	
	Tend to disagree	154	36%		166	46%		320	41%	
	Totally disagree	170	40%		92	26%		262	34%	
	100 Total	422	100%	3.09	357	100%	2.92	779	100%	3.01
Croatia	191 Totally agree	31	7%		35	11%		66	9%	
	Tend to agree	62	15%		59	19%		121	16%	
	Tend to disagree	156	37%		154	49%		310	42%	
	Totally disagree	176	41%		69	22%		245	33%	
	191 Total	425	100%	3.12	317	100%	2.81	742	100%	2.99

Cyprus	196	Totally agree	12	7%		17	12%		29	10%
		Tend to agree	16	10%		31	22%		47	16%
		Tend to disagree	45	27%		54	39%		99	33%
		Totally disagree	91	55%		36	26%		127	42%
	196 Total		164	100%	3.31	138	100%	2.79	302	100%
Czechia	203	Totally agree	30	7%		18	6%		48	6%
		Tend to agree	76	18%		59	18%		135	18%
		Tend to disagree	155	36%		170	52%		325	43%
		Totally disagree	164	39%		79	24%		243	32%
	203 Total		425	100%	3.07	326	100%	2.95	751	100%
Denmark	208	Totally agree	36	10%		20	7%		56	9%
		Tend to agree	71	19%		69	25%		140	22%
		Tend to disagree	128	35%		119	43%		247	39%
		Totally disagree	131	36%		66	24%		197	31%
	208 Total		366	100%	2.97	274	100%	2.84	640	100%
Estonia	233	Totally agree	27	7%		14	4%		41	6%
		Tend to agree	67	17%		77	23%		144	20%
		Tend to disagree	153	38%		182	54%		335	46%
		Totally disagree	153	38%		63	19%		216	29%
	233 Total		400	100%	3.08	336	100%	2.88	736	100%
Finland	246	Totally agree	25	6%		13	4%		38	5%
		Tend to agree	69	16%		52	17%		121	17%
		Tend to disagree	145	34%		149	49%		294	41%
		Totally disagree	183	43%		88	29%		271	37%
	246 Total		422	100%	3.15	302	100%	3.03	724	100%
France	250	Totally agree	35	8%		38	12%		73	10%
		Tend to agree	85	20%		83	26%		168	23%
		Tend to disagree	114	27%		118	37%		232	32%
		Totally disagree	184	44%		78	25%		262	36%
	250 Total		418	100%	3.07	317	100%	2.74	735	100%
Germany	276	Totally agree	47	10%		31	8%		78	9%
		Tend to agree	77	17%		68	17%		145	17%
		Tend to disagree	139	31%		161	41%		300	35%
		Totally disagree	191	42%		134	34%		325	38%
	276 Total		454	100%	3.04	394	100%	3.01	848	100%
Greece	300	Totally agree	25	6%		17	5%		42	5%
		Tend to agree	70	16%		66	21%		136	18%
		Tend to disagree	143	32%		150	47%		293	38%
		Totally disagree	207	47%		86	27%		293	38%
	300 Total		445	100%	3.20	319	100%	2.96	764	100%
Hungary	348	Totally agree	34	8%		30	8%		64	8%
		Tend to agree	71	17%		76	20%		147	19%
		Tend to disagree	114	28%		172	46%		286	36%
		Totally disagree	194	47%		100	26%		294	37%
	348 Total		413	100%	3.13	378	100%	2.90	791	100%
Ireland	372	Totally agree	31	8%		23	8%		54	8%
		Tend to agree	79	20%		61	21%		140	20%
		Tend to disagree	141	35%		138	46%		279	40%
		Totally disagree	153	38%		75	25%		228	33%
	372 Total		404	100%	3.03	297	100%	2.89	701	100%
	380	Totally agree	44	10%		41	10%		85	10%

		Tend to agree	78	18%		81	21%		159	19%	
		Tend to disagree	122	29%		155	39%		277	34%	
		Totally disagree	184	43%		117	30%		301	37%	
		380 Total	428	100%	3.04	394	100%	2.88	822	100%	2.97
Latvia	428	Totally agree	28	8%		14	4%		42	6%	
		Tend to agree	67	18%		80	24%		147	21%	
		Tend to disagree	136	37%		164	49%		300	42%	
		Totally disagree	141	38%		77	23%		218	31%	
		428 Total	372	100%	3.05	335	100%	2.91	707	100%	2.98
Lithuania	440	Totally agree	21	6%		19	6%		40	6%	
		Tend to agree	55	15%		61	18%		116	16%	
		Tend to disagree	143	38%		155	46%		298	42%	
		Totally disagree	157	42%		103	30%		260	36%	
		440 Total	376	100%	3.16	338	100%	3.01	714	100%	3.09
Luxembourg	442	Totally agree	12	5%		16	9%		28	7%	
		Tend to agree	40	17%		35	19%		75	18%	
		Tend to disagree	68	30%		71	38%		139	33%	
		Totally disagree	110	48%		65	35%		175	42%	
		442 Total	230	100%	3.20	187	100%	2.99	417	100%	3.11
Malta	470	Totally agree	14	6%		19	10%		33	8%	
		Tend to agree	21	9%		35	19%		56	13%	
		Tend to disagree	70	30%		58	31%		128	30%	
		Totally disagree	130	55%		73	39%		203	48%	
		470 Total	235	100%	3.34	185	100%	3.00	420	100%	3.19
Netherlands	528	Totally agree	47	11%		18	5%		65	9%	
		Tend to agree	63	15%		68	20%		131	17%	
		Tend to disagree	123	30%		127	38%		250	33%	
		Totally disagree	182	44%		122	36%		304	41%	
		528 Total	415	100%	3.06	335	100%	3.05	750	100%	3.06
Poland	616	Totally agree	40	10%		35	10%		75	10%	
		Tend to agree	84	21%		63	17%		147	19%	
		Tend to disagree	111	27%		178	49%		289	37%	
		Totally disagree	172	42%		90	25%		262	34%	
		616 Total	407	100%	3.02	366	100%	2.88	773	100%	2.95
Portugal	620	Totally agree	24	5%		26	6%		50	6%	
		Tend to agree	54	12%		61	15%		115	13%	
		Tend to disagree	117	26%		159	39%		276	32%	
		Totally disagree	249	56%		164	40%		413	48%	
		620 Total	444	100%	3.33	410	100%	3.12	854	100%	3.23
Romania	642	Totally agree	43	10%		41	10%		84	10%	
		Tend to agree	64	15%		69	18%		133	16%	
		Tend to disagree	144	33%		157	40%		301	36%	
		Totally disagree	180	42%		127	32%		307	37%	
		642 Total	431	100%	3.07	394	100%	2.94	825	100%	3.01
Slovakia	703	Totally agree	27	7%		27	8%		54	7%	
		Tend to agree	63	15%		73	21%		136	18%	
		Tend to disagree	158	39%		165	48%		323	43%	
		Totally disagree	159	39%		77	23%		236	32%	
		703 Total	407	100%	3.10	342	100%	2.85	749	100%	2.99
Slovenia	705	Totally agree	26	6%		23	7%		49	7%	
		Tend to agree	62	15%		67	21%		129	17%	

	Tend to disagree	159	38%		162	50%		321	43%	
	Totally disagree	169	41%		73	22%		242	33%	
	705 Total	416	100%	3.13	325	100%	2.88	741	100%	3.02
Spain	724 Totally agree	38	8%		35	9%		73	8%	
	Tend to agree	82	18%		86	21%		168	19%	
	Tend to disagree	127	28%		154	37%		281	32%	
	Totally disagree	207	46%		136	33%		343	40%	
	724 Total	454	100%	3.11	411	100%	2.95	865	100%	3.03
Sweden	752 Totally agree	25	7%		22	8%		47	7%	
	Tend to agree	85	22%		71	27%		156	24%	
	Tend to disagree	112	30%		87	33%		199	31%	
	Totally disagree	157	41%		80	31%		237	37%	
	752 Total	379	100%	3.06	260	100%	2.87	639	100%	2.98
Grand Total		10592		3.11	8781		2.93	19373		3.03

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